

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

THE SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF SUGAMMADEX IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC
RENAL FAILURE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Jillian Stasiun

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN, Team Leader
Sass Elisha, EdD, CRNA, FAAN, Team Member

December 2023

Author Note

Jillian Stasiun - <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-3064-161X>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17289253>

© 2023 Jillian Stasiun

ABSTRACT

Despite the absence of FDA approval, the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure (CrCl < 30 ml/min) is frequently observed in the clinical setting. The purpose of this project is to examine the literature regarding the efficacy and safety of sugammadex for reversing rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in adults with chronic renal failure and to generate evidence-based suggestions for practice. The literature was reviewed, and the results were complemented by an interview with an expert in the field. A presentation and manuscript were developed to ensure that this project's valuable insights and knowledge reached healthcare professionals. It was found that sugammadex may be a safe and effective reversal agent for rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in adult patients with severe renal failure undergoing general and renal transplantation surgery, but there is insufficient data to recommend its regular use. More robust prospective studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are warranted. Until more data is available, providers using sugammadex in this patient population can minimize patient risks by utilizing neuromuscular monitoring and adhering to dosing guidelines provided by the manufacturer.

Keywords: sugammadex, chronic renal failure, end-stage renal disease

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vi
BACKGROUND	1
SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK.....	6
Previous Use of the PRISMA 2020 Statement	6
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
Methods.....	8
Overview.....	8
Study Selection	8
Quality Assessment of Research Evidence.....	9
Ethical Considerations	9
Study Results	10
Identification of Studies.....	10
Quality Assessment.....	10
Study Participants' Level of Chronic Renal Failure	12
Variables and Measures	12
Findings.....	13
Efficacy	13
Pharmacokinetics	14
Dialysability	16
Safety	17
Renal Transplant.....	18
Summary.....	19
METHODS	21
RESULTS	22
Literature Review.....	22
Expert Insight.....	22
Dissemination	23

DISCUSSION	24
Anticipated Positive and Negative Unintended Consequences	24
Off-Label Drug Use	25
Limitations, Strengths & Recommendations	26
Suggestions for Practice.....	27
Conclusion	28
REFERENCES	29
APPENDIX A: PRISMA 2020 Checklist.....	41
APPENDIX B: Figure 1: PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram for New Systematic Reviews.....	43
APPENDIX C: JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence Guide	44
APPENDIX D: JHEBP Research Evidence Appraisal Tools.....	45
APPENDIX E: JHEBP Nonresearch Evidence Appraisal Tools.....	49
APPENDIX F: Figure 2: PRISMA Flow Diagram.....	51
APPENDIX G: Presentation for Anesthesia Providers	52
APPENDIX H: AANA Journal Manuscript	59

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I want to express my deepest gratitude and appreciation for the steadfast support, continual guidance, and encouragement from my Team Leader, Dr. Penny Weismuller, and my Team Member, Dr. Sass Elisha. Without them, this project would have been impossible. I also want to thank my husband and son for their unconditional love and patience.

Background

Neostigmine is conventionally the primary choice for reversing rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in individuals with chronic renal failure. However, there are limitations to its use and side effects that can negatively impact the patient (Hristovska et al., 2017; Thilen et al., 2023). Sugammadex is a selective relaxant binding agent associated with decreased time to complete blockade recovery and lower rates of residual neuromuscular blockade (NMB; Hristovska et al., 2017; Thilen et al., 2023). The current guidelines from the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) recommend the use of sugammadex across varying depths of blockade to mitigate the risk of residual NMB (Thilen et al., 2023). However, the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) advises caution against administering sugammadex to patients with severe renal impairment (creatinine clearance [CrCl] < 30 ml/min) due to insufficient safety data in this population (Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp., 2015). Despite the regulatory caution, there have been reports of sugammadex use in patients with severe renal failure. This deviation from formal recommendations has been documented in various clinical reports, shedding light on the nuanced decisions made in real-world medical scenarios (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Kurita et al., 2016; Lobaz et al., 2013; Navare et al., 2019; Ono et al., 2018; Pfaff et al., 2019).

Neostigmine is an anticholinesterase commonly used to reverse NMB induced by aminosteroidal or benzylisoquinoline non-depolarizing muscle relaxants (NDMR; Lien, 2023). As an anticholinesterase, neostigmine inhibits the breakdown of the neurotransmitter acetylcholine (ACh), which increases the amount of ACh available to compete with NDMR bound to nicotinic-acetylcholine receptors (nAChR) at the neuromuscular junction (NMJ; Amneal Pharmaceuticals, 2020). As NDMRs become displaced from the nAChR in favor of ACh, normal muscle function is restored. However, neostigmine also increases ACh activity at

muscarinic receptors, eliciting undesirable cholinergic side effects, including bradycardia, bronchoconstriction, nausea, vomiting, and gastrointestinal hypermotility (Amneal Pharmaceuticals, 2020). To circumvent these side effects, a muscarinic receptor antagonist (e.g., glycopyrrolate) is given concomitantly with neostigmine when reversing NMB (Amneal Pharmaceuticals, 2020). However, administering anticholinergics has additional side effects like dry mouth, urinary retention, constipation, and tachycardia (Exela Pharma Sciences, 2018).

In addition to unwanted side effects, there are additional disadvantages associated with neostigmine administration. Neostigmine cannot adequately reverse profound and deep blockade (i.e., 1 to 2 posttetanic count) due to a ceiling effect in which large or additional doses fail to provide further reversal of NMB (Amneal Pharmaceuticals, 2020; Tajaate et al., 2018). To minimize the risks of residual NMB, neostigmine is no longer recommended for reversing moderate depths of blockade (train-of-four count of 1 to 2; Tajaate et al., 2018; Thilen et al., 2023). For shallow depths of blockade, the optimal dose of neostigmine is variable and dependent on a multitude of factors, including depth of blockade at the time of reversal, type of neuromuscular monitoring used, half-life of neuromuscular blocking agent (NMBA) administered, and other anesthetics given (Luo et al., 2018). The lack of clear dosing guidelines can lead to under- or over-dosing of neostigmine and residual NMB (Kent et al., 2018; Luo et al., 2018).

Residual NMB is an inadequate neuromuscular recovery from NMBA administration (Hristovska et al., 2017). Measurement of neuromuscular function is recommended at the adductor pollicis by a quantitative neuromuscular monitor that provides a ratio between the first and fourth muscle twitch (Hristovska et al., 2017; Thilen et al., 2023). Signs and symptoms of residual NMB, such as pharyngeal dysfunction, impaired swallowing, and decreased upper

esophageal sphincter tone, have been reported at a train-of-four ratio (TOFr) of less than 0.9 (Cedborg et al., 2014). Thus, satisfactory recovery from NMB is commonly defined as a TOFr greater than or equal to 0.9 (Hristovska et al., 2017).

Despite the introduction of reversal agents, postoperative residual NMB remains a persistent clinical issue (16-60%) that negatively impacts the patient population (Aragón-Benedí et al., 2022; Fortier et al., 2015; Hristovska et al., 2017; Raval et al., 2020; Saager et al., 2019). Postoperative residual NMB is associated with postoperative pulmonary complications (POPC) such as respiratory failure, reintubation, atelectasis, and pneumonia (Davies et al., 2017). Even mild POPC (e.g., prolonged oxygen therapy, atelectasis) can increase intensive care unit (ICU) admissions, hospital length of stay, and postoperative morbidity and mortality (Fernandez-Bustamante et al., 2017). Studies examining various reversal agents and neuromuscular monitoring techniques have reported lower rates of residual NMB with the use of sugammadex and quantitative neuromuscular monitoring (Hristovska et al., 2017; Thilen et al., 2023). However, the evidence showing a corresponding reduction in POPC with the use of sugammadex is still conflicting (Kheterpal et al., 2020; Murphy et al., 2021; Thilen et al., 2023). Yet the evidence and patient impact is profound enough for the ASA to recommend the use of quantitative neuromuscular monitoring and sugammadex for reversing all depths of rocuronium and vecuronium-induced NMB (Thilen et al., 2023).

Sugammadex is a selective relaxant binding agent that does not utilize a receptor system and thus does not elicit cholinergic side effects (Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp., 2015). It is a modified gamma cyclodextrin that reverses NMB by encapsulating and binding the NMBA (Hristovska et al., 2017; Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp., 2015). Once encapsulated, the NMBA is inactive and unavailable to bind to nAChRs at the NMJ (Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp., 2015).

Since sugammadex was explicitly designed to encapsulate rocuronium, it has a high association constant and a low dissociation constant for rocuronium (Bom et al., 2002). Sugammadex has also been shown to bind other aminosteroidal NMBAs such as vecuronium and, to a lesser extent, pancuronium but is ineffective with benzyloisoquinolines (e.g., cisatracurium; Hristovska et al., 2017)

Sugammadex has several advantages and a few disadvantages. When compared to neostigmine, sugammadex has been shown to reverse all depths of NMB, reach full blockade recovery faster, and decrease rates of residual NMB and postoperative adverse events (e.g., bradycardia, PONV, desaturation, need for supplementary oxygen; Hristovska et al., 2017; Thilen et al., 2023). However, hypersensitivity reactions (ranging from a mild rash to anaphylaxis) and bradycardia (possibly resulting in cardiac arrest) have been reported with sugammadex administration (Bologheanu et al., 2022; Fierro et al., 2021; Miyazaki et al., 2018). Although infrequent, the risk of these severe side effects increases with larger doses (Merck & Co., 2023a). Sugammadex is not currently recommended in patients with severe renal impairment, as there are concerns about prolonged exposure to the drug (Merck & Co., 2023a; Paredes et al., 2020).

Chronic renal failure (CRF) is defined as the progressive loss of kidney function that eventually leads to the need for renal replacement therapy (Vaidya & Aeddula, 2022). Patients with CRF commonly have multiple comorbidities (e.g., hypertension, diabetes, cardiovascular disease) that increase their risk of perioperative complications (Kanda et al., 2017; Palamuthusingam et al., 2021). Systematic reviews and meta-analyses reported that patients receiving chronic dialysis have increased risks of postoperative infection, cardiovascular

complications, and mortality (Palamuthusingam et al., 2020; Palamuthusingam et al., 2021). Therefore, careful perioperative management of patients with CRF is crucial.

Since sugammadex is not recommended for patients with severe kidney failure, neostigmine is the predominant reversal agent in this patient population. However, given that neostigmine and glycopyrrolate are both partially excreted by the kidneys, their elimination half-life is also prolonged in those with renal failure (Amneal Pharmaceuticals, 2020; Exela Pharma Sciences, 2018), potentially increasing the risk of side effects. Additionally, due to the complexity of CRF and the benefits of sugammadex, situations arise where sugammadex may be the safest option for the patient (e.g., cannot ventilate, cannot intubate situations). Moreover, there have been reports of sugammadex being utilized in patients with CRF on dialysis without adverse outcomes (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Navare et al., 2019). Considering the benefits of sugammadex, more research needs to be conducted to compile what is currently known about the use of sugammadex in patients with chronic renal failure.

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to examine literature regarding the efficacy and safety of sugammadex as a reversal agent for rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in adults with chronic renal failure. This project aims to generate evidence-based suggestions that will guide providers in selecting the most appropriate neuromuscular blocking and reversal agent for patients with chronic renal failure.

Supporting Framework

Literature reviews are essential in medical science because they facilitate evidence-based clinical decision-making by providing a comprehensive and critical evaluation of the existing literature on specific topics (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a). Systematic reviews are a type of literature review that utilizes rigorous methodology to synthesize research findings (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a). However, the value of a systematic review is contingent upon the study results and how well researchers report their methodology and findings (Moher et al., 2009). Due to the frequency of inadequate reporting in systematic reviews and meta-analyses, an international group of experts created a set of guidelines called the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) Statement that serves as a framework aimed to improve the quality, transparency, and reproducibility of these types of studies (Moher et al., 2009; Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a). Recently updated in 2020, the PRISMA Statement includes a 27-item checklist (Appendix A) covering all sections of a manuscript and flow diagram templates (Figure 1, Appendix B) to illustrate the study selection process (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a). The authors also published the PRISMA Explanation and Elaboration Document to be used alongside the PRISMA Statement to provide clarity and facilitate the use of the guidelines (Page, Moher, et al., 2021). The PRISMA 2020 Statement will serve as a framework for this DNP project. It will guide the production of a highly structured general review of the current literature on the efficacy and safety of sugammadex for rocuronium-induced NM blockade in adults with chronic renal failure.

Previous Use of the PRISMA 2020 Statement

Since 2021, the PRISMA Statement has been published in multiple journals (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a, 2021b, 2021c), accessed over 200,000 times (British Medical Journal,

2023), and cited in over 20,000 articles (Altmetric, n.d.). Twenty-seven percent of medical journals (Tao et al., 2011) and 28% of nursing journals (Tam et al., 2017) now recommend or require authors to utilize the PRISMA Statement as a prerequisite for submission. In a 2018 study, Sun et al. evaluated the reporting quality of systematic reviews and meta-analyses of nursing interventions in patients with Alzheimer's disease published before and after the inception of the PRISMA Statement. It was found that the reporting quality of systematic reviews and meta-analyses had improved after the publication of the guidelines (Sun et al., 2018). These results led authors to suggest that endorsement of the PRISMA Statement by more journal articles may lead to improved quality of articles and, thus, more reliable evidence available to nurses (Sun et al., 2018). The guidance of a checklist and quality of reviews provided by the utility of the PRISMA Statement make it a sound framework for this project. However, items on the checklist that are outside the scope of this project were omitted.

Review of Literature

Methods

Overview

The literature review was conducted using the research databases PubMed, Cochrane, and CINAHL. Combinations of the following keywords were used in the search: “sugammadex,” “renal failure,” “kidney failure,” “chronic renal failure,” “chronic kidney disease,” “kidney disease,” “end-stage renal disease,” and “renal impairment.” Inclusion criteria included full-text articles published within the last ten years, written in English, and pertained to the use of sugammadex in patients with renal disease. This timeframe was selected because it allowed for the inclusion of research conducted after FDA approval of sugammadex in 2015 (Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp., 2015). Due to the pharmacokinetic impact of age, pregnancy, and species, articles on pediatrics, parturients, and animal models were excluded. Studies on vecuronium-induced blockade were also excluded as it was not the focus of this review. The identified articles were reviewed and examined individually for evidence related to the pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, safety, and efficacy of sugammadex as a reversal of rocuronium-induced NMB in patients with chronic renal failure. Citation chaining was also performed to identify key authors and publications relevant to this review’s purpose.

Study Selection

The inclusion of studies in the review was based on predefined eligibility criteria and determined by one reviewer using a two-step process. All publications were first screened by title and abstract. Those that met the criteria then underwent a complete review of the text. Most studies were published within the predefined time restriction. However, citation chaining

resulted in the procurement of three seminal articles published outside the 10-year time frame (Cammu et al., 2012; Staals et al., 2008; Staals et al., 2010)

Quality Assessment of Research Evidence

The quality and reliability of evidence were evaluated using the Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice (JHEBP) Model and Tools (Dang et al., 2022). The level of evidence for each article was categorized using the JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence Guide (Appendix C). Levels I and II on the hierarchy include experimental study designs (randomized control trials, systematic reviews, experimental, quasi-experimental) and are considered the strongest types of evidence. Non-experimental research, such as observational and qualitative studies, are considered Level III evidence. Level IV includes scientifically based clinical practice guidelines and position statements published by nationally recognized expert committees or consensus panels. Experiential and nonresearch evidence, such as case reports and various types of literature reviews, are the lowest types of evidence and fall under Level V. After categorization of evidence, the quality was determined using the JHEBP Evidence Appraisal Tools (Appendix D; Appendix E), resulting in the assignment of high, good, or low quality ratings (Dang et al., 2022).

Ethical Considerations

The project proposal was evaluated by a designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California Institutional Review Board (IRB). It was determined that the literature review is not considered human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 e (1) and (l) and is therefore exempt from IRB approval.

Results

Identification of Studies

The electronic database search yielded 46 articles with duplicates removed (Figure 2, Appendix F). All 46 article titles and abstracts were screened for inclusion. After 29 articles were excluded, full texts of the remaining 17 articles were assessed for eligibility. Three articles were removed after full-text screening, resulting in 14 articles from the database search that met eligibility criteria. Additionally, five articles were identified from citation chaining, assessed, met criteria, and therefore included. Overall, a total of 19 articles were included in the literature review.

Quality Assessment

Most of the evidence collected belonged to Levels III and V on the JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence (Appendix C). Of the 19 articles, there were six quasi-experimental studies (Level II), one systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies (Level III), two retrospective cohort studies (Level III), four retrospective case-controlled observational studies (Level III), and six case reports (Level V).

Half of the case reports were found to be “high quality” evidence (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Kurita et al., 2016; Lobaz et al., 2013), while the remaining half met the criteria for “good quality” (Navare et al., 2019; Ono et al., 2018; Pfaff et al., 2019). In those considered “high quality,” the purpose of the case report was clearly stated, the report was clearly presented, the findings were supported by relevant research, and the recommendations were clearly stated and linked to the findings (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Kurita et al., 2016; Lobaz et al., 2013). The

case reports that were considered “good quality” did not have clear recommendations (Navare et al., 2019; Ono et al., 2018; Pfaff et al., 2019)

Three retrospective case-controlled studies investigated the impact of sugammadex on post-renal transplant recovery outcomes (Arslantas & Cevik, 2019; Carron et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2021). While the study by Carron et al. (2022) was deemed “high quality,” the other two were categorized as “good quality” due to their reliance on older studies in their literature reviews and a lack of rationale for their chosen sample sizes (Arslantas & Cevik, 2019; Vargas et al., 2021). The last retrospective case-controlled study looked at mortality rates after the use of sugammadex in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD; Song et al., 2022). Upon assessment, it was considered “good quality” instead of “high quality” due to the use of older studies (Song et al., 2022).

Both retrospective cohort studies examined specific clinical outcomes as indicators of the safety profile of sugammadex in patients with ESRD (Adams et al., 2020; Paredes et al., 2020). The study by Paredes et al. (2020) was categorized as “high quality” because there was a clear presentation of the problem, gaps in knowledge, study’s purpose, data collection methods, and results. The authors also utilized current sources, justified sample size, discussed limitations, and made conclusions based on results (Paredes et al., 2020). Adams et al. (2020) included older sources in their literature review but had many positive aspects that made the evidence “good quality.” The systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies met “high quality” criteria with its well-defined topic, clear search method, thorough evaluation and synthesis of the literature, appropriate recommendations, and definitive conclusions (Kim et al., 2021).

The prospective studies examined in this review were considered quasi-experimental studies due to the absence of either a control group or randomization among study participants

(Cammu et al., 2012; de Souza et al., 2015; Min et al., 2017; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008; Staals et al., 2010). All quasi-experimental studies met the criteria for “good quality” except for one (Cammu et al., 2012). The study by Cammu et al. (2012) was found to be “poor quality” because of their sample size of six participants, thereby reducing the external validity of their findings.

Study Participants’ Level of Chronic Renal Failure

While the literature search did not limit the degree of renal impairment in individuals with chronic renal failure, the resultant literature evidence focused on adult patients with severe (CrCl <30 ml/min) or end-stage renal failure (CrCl <15 ml/min). Only Min et al. (2017) included patients with moderate renal failure (CrCl 30 to 50 ml/min) in addition to those with severe disease. Some study participants required some form of dialysis (hemodialysis or peritoneal) due to the severity of their disease, but it was not a requirement in all studies.

Within the literature evidence, several terms have been utilized interchangeably to describe the same degree of renal impairment. The terms “severe renal impairment,” “severe renal failure,” and “severe renal insufficiency” have all been used to describe participants with a CrCl <30 ml/min. Articles employing the terms “end-stage renal failure” or “end-stage renal disease” did not provide an associated creatinine clearance or glomerular filtration rate (GFR). However, these terms, along with “chronic kidney disease stage 5,” are commonly associated with the staging of chronic kidney disease from the National Kidney Foundation, which defines ESRD as a GFR < 15ml/min (Vaidya & Aeddula, 2022).

Variables and Measures

The studies’ key variables and measures encompassed various aspects of efficacy and safety, such as the time required to achieve complete NMB reversal, NMB recurrence or

recurarization, the incidence of reintubation, delayed extubation, adverse events (AEs), hypersensitivity, hypoxemia, pneumonia, mortality, postoperative respiratory complications, acute rejection episodes, graft failure, hospital length of stay, postoperative ICU admission, and renal function laboratory tests. Several studies also measured pharmacokinetic factors, specifically plasma and urine concentrations of rocuronium and sugammadex, area under the curve (AUC), elimination half-life, and mean residence time.

Findings

Efficacy

Numerous studies have investigated the effectiveness of sugammadex as a reversal agent for moderate and deep levels of rocuronium-induced NMB in patients with severe renal failure (de Souza et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008). In a multicenter prospective clinical trial conducted by Staals et al. (2008), a 2.0 mg/kg dose of sugammadex was utilized to reverse moderate depths of NMB (reappearance of the second TOF twitch or T2). Researchers found that patients with severe renal failure took longer to fully recover ($\text{TOFr} \geq 0.9$) than those with normal renal function, with a mean recovery time of 2.0 ± 0.72 minutes and 1.65 ± 0.63 minutes, respectively. However, the difference between the two groups was not statistically significant (Staals et al., 2008). Two comparative studies that examined the reversal of deep NMB (1 to 2 post-tetanic count) using 4.0 mg/kg of sugammadex also found a prolonged time to full recovery in patients with severe renal failure (de Souza et al., 2015; Panhuizen et al., 2015). Panhuizen et al. (2015) observed a median [95% confidence interval] time to full recovery at 3.1 [2.4 - 4.6] minutes in the renal failure group and 1.9 [1.6 - 2.8] minutes in the control group. Similarly, de Souza et al. (2015) reported a mean time to full recovery of 5.6 ± 3.6 minutes in the ESRD group and 2.7 ± 1.3 minutes in the control group. A

systematic review and meta-analysis of six prospective case-control studies reported a weighted mean difference of 1.14 [0.29 - 2.00] minutes in time to TOFr \geq 0.9 between patients with ESRD and patients with normal renal function (Kim et al., 2021). Despite these delays in recovery time, all four studies concluded that sugammadex could rapidly and reliably reverse NMB in patients with severe renal failure (de Souza et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008).

Sugammadex's effectiveness in reversing NMB among patients with severe renal failure has been documented across various clinical settings through case reports (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Kurita et al., 2016; Lobaz et al., 2013; Navare et al., 2019; Pfaff et al., 2019). Two case reports described patients with ESRD who experienced progressive NMB due to the inadvertent subcutaneous administration of rocuronium through an infiltrated peripheral intravenous catheter during induction (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Navare et al., 2019). In these cases, the administration of sugammadex at the end of surgery led to the cessation of the progression of NMB and complete recovery (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Navare et al., 2019). Lobaz et al. (2013) reported a case where sugammadex was successfully utilized as a rescue agent after the initial reversal with neostigmine led to postoperative recurarization. A retrospective observational study described similar reports of using sugammadex as a rescue drug for inadequate reversal with neostigmine (Adams et al., 2020). Overall, the case reports illustrate sugammadex as a valuable option for managing NMB in patients with severe renal failure, especially in cases where neostigmine has proven ineffective or unsuitable (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Lobaz et al., 2013; Navare et al., 2019; Pfaff et al., 2019).

Pharmacokinetics

Pharmacokinetic (PK) studies of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure have demonstrated significant changes in the drug's metabolism and clearance (Min et al., 2017; Staals et al., 2010). Studies found a correlation between creatinine clearance and sugammadex clearance, such that as renal function declines, plasma clearance of sugammadex decreases. With decreased plasma clearance, patients with severe renal failure exhibited increased PK parameters that suggest prolonged exposure to sugammadex. More specifically, Staals et al. (2010) reported a 15-20-fold increase in the area under the curve (AUC), elimination half-life, and mean residence time, and a 17-fold decrease in the creatinine clearance of sugammadex. Despite a decreased clearance, plasma concentrations of sugammadex were undetectable after seven days post-dose in those with severe renal failure (Min et al., 2017).

The impact of severe renal failure on the pharmacokinetics of rocuronium was similar to that of sugammadex, although less pronounced (Staals et al., 2010). When comparing the plasma clearance of sugammadex and rocuronium in patients with ESRD, sugammadex had a slower mean total plasma clearance (5.5 ml/min) than rocuronium (41.8 ml/min) due to rocuronium's extra-renal means of metabolism and excretion (Staals et al., 2010). As a result, sugammadex plasma concentrations may remain elevated in those with ESRD during the postoperative period, thereby reducing the probability of unbound rocuronium (Kim et al., 2021).

In the PK analysis conducted by Panhuizen et al. (2015), 34 patients with severe renal failure who received sugammadex to reverse rocuronium-induced NMB were compared to a control group of 33 patients with normal renal function. Plasma concentrations of both drugs were measured at various time intervals. Among the participants with severe renal failure, measurable concentrations of rocuronium were observed in six individuals seven days after administration, but no detectable concentrations were found on Day 28. The presence of

sugammadex alongside rocuronium was not reported, as the PK analysis of sugammadex conducted by the same researchers was deemed invalid due to its failure to meet the quality standards set by Merck & Co., Inc. Nonetheless, considering the PK findings in Staals et al. (2010), sugammadex could hypothetically be present seven days post-dose, which contrasts with the findings reported in Min et al. (2017).

Dialysability

Several studies have explored the dialysability of sugammadex and the sugammadex-rocuronium complex, including two clinical trials and one case report (Cammu et al., 2012; Kurita et al., 2016; Staals et al., 2010). In a prospective clinical trial by Staals et al. (2010), low-flux hemodialysis (HD) was not found to significantly reduce the plasma concentration of sugammadex. However, high-flux HD, which uses a more permeable filter, was found to be more effective (Cammu et al., 2012). In a single-center, open-label trial, six ICU patients with severe renal failure were dialyzed with a high-flux filter after 4.0 mg/kg of sugammadex was administered to reverse 0.6 mg/kg of rocuronium (Cammu et al., 2012). Researchers reported a 69% reduction in sugammadex and a 75% reduction in rocuronium after the first dialysis session and approximately a 50% reduction in both drugs in subsequent sessions (Cammu et al., 2012).

A case report by Kurita et al. (2016) demonstrated similar reduction ratios in a HD patient who received rocuronium and sugammadex for electroconvulsive therapy (ECT). The patient received a 0.6 mg/kg dose of rocuronium followed by 2.0 mg/kg of sugammadex for each bi-weekly ECT session. Between ECT sessions, she underwent high-flux HD that resulted in an average reduction of 61.9% of sugammadex and its complex with rocuronium, consistent with the findings of Cammu et al. (2012). Despite having HD three times a week, the frequency at which she received sugammadex resulted in an accumulation of free sugammadex that led to a

slight reduction in the efficacy of rocuronium during ECT sessions six through eight. While it is uncommon for HD patients to receive sugammadex regularly, this case report emphasizes the importance of diligent NM monitoring and appropriate dosing in this patient population.

Safety

Given the potential safety concerns associated with the prolonged exposure of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure, researchers have examined the incidence of sugammadex-related AEs and recurarization (Cammu et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2021; Min et al., 2017; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Paredes et al., 2020; Staals et al., 2008). Three studies monitored the presence of recurrent NMB or recurarization after achieving full recovery with sugammadex (Adams et al., 2020; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008). None of these studies found evidence of recurarization during the postoperative period of 24 to 48 hours in patients with severe renal failure (Adams et al., 2020; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008). These findings were corroborated by a systematic review and meta-analysis that reported no difference in the incidence of NMB recurrence between patients with ESRD and those with normal renal function (Kim et al., 2021). However, acceleromyography-determined recurarization in a control patient with normal renal function was noted in a study by Panhuizen et al. (2015). It was suggested that an insufficient dose of sugammadex (4 mg/kg) given only five minutes after an intubating dose of rocuronium may have been responsible for the recurrence, and a higher dose (16 mg/kg) during the onset of NMB may have been more appropriate (Panhuizen et al., 2015).

The incidence of AEs in patients with severe renal disease who received sugammadex varied across the studies. Cammu et al. (2012), Kim et al. (2021), and Panhuizen et al. (2015) reported no significant AEs related to sugammadex administration in patients with severe renal failure. Additionally, a retrospective propensity score-matched study by Song et al. (2022) found

no significant difference in 30-day and 1-year mortality rates in ESRD patients who received sugammadex compared to those who did not. However, three studies reported possible sugammadex-related AEs in patients with ESRD (Paredes et al., 2020; Min et al., 2017; Staals et al., 2008). Paredes et al. (2020) found that among 219 ESRD patients who received sugammadex, 18 experienced pulmonary complications such as pneumonia, hypoxemia, and reintubation within 30 postoperative days. Although the authors did not believe these complications were likely related to NMB management, they could not completely rule out the possibility of sugammadex contributing to the AEs for six of these patients due to the absence of quantitative NM monitoring. In Min et al. (2017), four patients with severe renal failure experienced possible sugammadex-related AEs such as extremity pain, dizziness, headache, and oral paresthesia. Staals et al. (2008) reported a total of eight AEs, occurring within 48 hours postoperatively, that could have been associated with sugammadex in five patients, two of whom were in the renally impaired group and three in the control group. These AEs included diarrhea, nausea, anesthesia complications, headache, and decreased oxygen saturation. While no serious sugammadex-related AEs were observed in patients with severe renal failure, most researchers felt that there was insufficient data on the safety profile of sugammadex to support the recommended use of sugammadex as a reversal agent for this patient population.

Renal Transplant

The use of sugammadex as a reversal agent after renal transplant surgery poses additional concerns surrounding its impact on grafted kidney function. Three retrospective case-control cohort studies compared grafted kidney function in patients who received sugammadex versus those who received neostigmine (Arslantas & Cervik, 2019; Carron et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2021). While rocuronium was the main NMBA utilized in Arslantas and Cervik (2019), Carron

et al. (2022) and Vargas et al. (2021) compared the rocuronium-sugammadex and cisatracurium-neostigmine strategies. These studies reviewed laboratory measures such as serum urea and creatinine, serum and urinary electrolytes, and estimated glomerular filtration rate, as well as AEs including acute rejection episodes, graft failure, hospital and post-anesthesia care unit length of stay, postoperative ICU admission, and NMB recurrence (Arslantas & Cervik, 2019; Carron et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2021). Researchers reported lower serum creatinine and urea levels in the sugammadex group than in the neostigmine group during the initial 24 hours post-transplantation (Carron et al., 2022; Vargas et al., 2021). In patients with ESRD, the use of sugammadex did not appear to increase the risk of acute kidney injury after transplantation (Vargas et al., 2021). Additionally, the sugammadex group exhibited lower incidences of severe postoperative hypoxemia and ICU admissions and shorter post-anesthesia care unit stays (Carron et al., 2022). In a case series of 99 patients, no AEs or signs of NMB recurrence were observed in the first 72 hours post-transplantation or at a six-month follow-up (Ono et al., 2018). These results were consistent with those reported by Arslantas and Cervik (2019), where no serious AEs were observed, and no differences in rejection and 28-day mortality rates between the sugammadex and neostigmine groups. Overall, the studies suggest that sugammadex may be safe and effective during renal transplantation, but the generalizability of their findings in the clinical setting may be limited.

Summary

Sugammadex is an effective reversal agent for moderate and deep NMB in patients with severe renal failure (de Souza et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008). However, careful NM monitoring and sugammadex dosing are critical to avoid the risk of complications resulting from under or overdosage (Kurita et al. 2016; Panhuizen et al. 2015).

Pharmacokinetic studies have shown that sugammadex clearance decreases as renal function declines, resulting in prolonged exposure to the drug (Min et al., 2017; Staals et al., 2010). However, plasma concentrations of sugammadex were undetectable after seven days post-dose in patients with ESRD (Min et al., 2017). Additionally, there is evidence that high-flux HD effectively reduces plasma concentrations of sugammadex (Cammu et al., 2012; Kurita et al., 2016; Staals et al., 2010). Studies that investigated the consequences of prolonged exposure found limited reports of AEs and no cases of recurarization (Cammu et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2021; Min et al., 2017; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Paredes et al., 2020; Staals et al., 2008). Similar efficacy and safety findings were reported when sugammadex was utilized during renal transplantation (Arslantas & Cevik, 2019; Carron et al., 2022; de Souza et al., 2015; Ono et al., 2018; Vargas et al., 2021). All in all, sugammadex may be a valuable option for the management of NMB in patients with severe renal failure, but not enough data is available to support the recommended use of sugammadex in this population

Methods

While neostigmine is currently the prevailing choice for reversing rocuronium-induced NMB in patients with chronic renal failure, it has limitations and potential side effects that can lead to adverse consequences for this patient population. In contrast, sugammadex has demonstrated greater efficiency and effectiveness as a reversal agent when compared to neostigmine. However, its use is not currently recommended in patients with severe renal failure due to limited safety data. Nevertheless, several case reports have documented its utilization in various clinical scenarios within this population (Doshu-Kajiura et al., 2021; Kurita et al., 2016; Lobaz et al., 2013; Navare et al., 2019; Ono et al., 2018; Pfaff et al., 2019). Further exploration of the current literature was warranted to better understand the safety and efficacy of sugammadex in patients with chronic renal failure.

A literature search and review were conducted and reported under the guidance of the PRISMA statement (Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a). To augment this analysis, an expert in the field was interviewed to investigate unpublished findings from ongoing studies and to obtain invaluable expert insights. The culmination of this DNP project was documented in a manuscript, providing a comprehensive record of the research outcomes and their implications. The extensive findings derived from the literature review and expert interviews were shared with the anesthesia department at Kaiser Permanente West Los Angeles through a 20-minute presentation (Appendix G), which ensured that the valuable insights and knowledge acquired through this project reached healthcare professionals in the field.

Results

Literature Review

A literature search on the utilization of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure revealed a scarcity of robust research on the subject. Among the limited articles that met the predefined eligibility criteria, the majority provided mid to low levels of evidence. Notably, no randomized controlled trials were found. Nevertheless, despite the lower levels of evidence, articles evaluating the same measures yielded consistent results. Studies investigating the efficacy of sugammadex have determined it to be effective in reversing various depths of rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in patients with severe renal failure (de Souza et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008). Pharmacokinetic investigations revealed reduced clearance of sugammadex in the presence of reduced kidney function, leading to an extended exposure to the drug (Min et al., 2017; Staals et al., 2010). Despite this prolonged exposure, there was no evidence of significant AEs or recurarization. Comparable efficacy and safety outcomes were obtained when sugammadex was used during renal transplantation (Arslantas & Cevik, 2019; Carron et al., 2022; de Souza et al., 2015; Ono et al., 2018; Vargas et al., 2021).

Expert Insight

On May 8, 2023, there was an interview over Zoom with a representative from Merck & Co., Inc. regarding recommendations concerning the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure. While there are no reports of recurarization or major adverse events, Merck & Co., Inc. has no immediate intentions to seek an advisory reversal from the FDA. Several reasons were cited, including the significant challenge of providing conclusive evidence to overturn the FDA's stance. Additionally, the considerable time and financial resources for such an

undertaking could be more effectively utilized in addressing a broader demographic, such as the pediatric population. Officially, Merck & Co., Inc. does not endorse the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure, including those on dialysis. Nevertheless, the decision to administer any medication ultimately rests with the provider's professional judgment. Off-label drug use may potentially expose the provider to legal repercussions in the event of a negative outcome.

Dissemination

Research findings were shared with Kaiser Permanente West Los Angeles anesthesia providers on September 29, 2023. There was an in-person attendance of 30 people, with additional individuals viewing on Zoom. After the presentation, several attendees raised questions, and a few expressed gratitude for the lecture and interest in the subject matter. To further disseminate study results, a manuscript was prepared according to the guidelines provided by the American Association of Nurse Anesthesiology (AANA) Journal for possible publication (Appendix H).

Discussion

The aims of this DNP project were to develop evidence-based suggestions for clinical practice and equip healthcare providers with a comprehensive understanding of the safety and efficacy of sugammadex in patients with CRF. Findings of the literature review and expert opinion were assessed and utilized to produce a presentation and manuscript, which are appended for reference. The information was well-received when presented to the anesthesia department at Kaiser West Los Angeles. If the manuscript were published, it would have the potential to reach a broader audience.

Anticipated Positive and Negative Unintended Consequences

An unintended positive consequence of this project could be an increased use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure. With no reported cases of re-renalization or significant AEs, healthcare providers might find greater confidence in using sugammadex in this population. The increased use of sugammadex may generate additional data and enrich the existing body of evidence that is currently lacking. This holds paramount importance because the progression of new research may be impeded as Merck & Co., Inc. has no plans for further investigation. Furthermore, the patent for sugammadex is set to expire in January 2026, allowing for generic manufacturing and sales at a lower cost (Merck & Co., 2023b). A lower price implies diminished funds for drug proprietors to support research (Wittich et al., 2012). United States FDA approval for the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure may never materialize. Consequently, healthcare providers will need to depend on existing research to inform their practice.

If this project leads to an increased utilization of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure, an unintended negative consequence could be inadvertent harm to the patient. The

absence of AEs in the literature does not guarantee that issues will not arise. The increased usage might uncover adverse effects that were previously concealed due to limited data availability.

Off-Label Drug Use

Given that the FDA does not currently recommend the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal impairment ($\text{CrCl} < 30 \text{ ml/min}$), using it in this population would fall under off-label drug use (OLDU). Off-label drug use involves the prescription or administration of a medication in a manner not approved by the FDA (U.S. FDA, 2018). However, it is important to note that the absence of FDA approval does not make its use illegal (Van Norman, 2023). Since the FDA does not regulate the practice of medicine, the decision to prescribe or administer an unapproved drug ultimately lies within the discretion of the healthcare provider (U.S. FDA, 2018). Anesthesia providers frequently engage in this commonplace and legally accepted practice, such as administering dexamethasone or propofol to prevent postoperative nausea (Wittich et al., 2012). However, it is an ethical and professional duty for healthcare providers to prioritize the patient's best interests and ground their OLDU decision in strong scientific evidence or medical opinion (Van Norman, 2023).

Enhancing patient safety and minimizing liability in OLDU requires providers to possess an in-depth understanding of both the medication and the patient (U.S. FDA, 2018; Joshi & Frierson, 2020; Van Norman, 2023; Wittich et al., 2012). This comprehensive knowledge should include an understanding of the drug's pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics and the latest research from reliable sources (Joshi & Frierson, 2020; Van Norman, 2023). Additionally, providers should be able to provide a scientific or clinical rationale for why the chosen off-label drug is the most suitable option for their patient at that specific moment (Joshi & Frierson, 2020; Van Norman, 2023). Some sources recommend obtaining informed consent from the patient

before OLDU, but it is not a legal requirement (Joshi & Frierson, 2020; Van Norman, 2023).

Lastly, there should be scrupulous documentation of the clinical assessment, rationale, consent (if obtained), and any adverse events that may have occurred (Joshi & Frierson, 2020; Van Norman, 2023).

Strengths, Limitations, and Recommendations

A limitation of this project is the scarcity of robust data. Most articles were Level III and IV on the JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence (Appendix C). All but one of the quasi-experimental studies had small sample sizes, limiting the generalizability of the data (Cammu et al., 2012; de Souza et al., 2015; Min et al., 2017; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008; Staals et al., 2010). Most studies had short postoperative observation periods, with only four studies and one case report extending their observation to 28 days and beyond (Arslantas & Cevik, 2019; Ono et al., 2018; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Paredes et al., 2020; Song et al., 2022). Considering that Panhuizen et al. (2015) detected rocuronium, and potentially sugammadex, after seven days but not after 28 days, future studies should consider an observation period of at least 28 days postoperatively.

Despite the limitations, there was consistency in the results and conclusions among studies. Articles examining efficacy consistently found sugammadex as an effective agent for reversing NMB in patients with severe renal failure (Carron et al., 2022; de Souza et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Staals et al., 2008). Similarly, studies on safety consistently reported no issues with recurarization or major AEs (Adams et al., 2020; Arslantas & Cevik, 2019; Carron et al., 2022; de Souza et al., 2015; Kim et al., 2021; Panhuizen et al., 2015; Paredes et al., 2020; Song et al., 2022; Staals et al., 2008). Another strength of the literature was its overall quality. Despite being lower levels of evidence, most studies were

considered “high” or “good quality”, except for one “poor quality” article (Cammu et al., 2012). While randomized-controlled trials are preferred, high quality low level data can still contribute to building a consensus. Currently, there is not enough data to recommend the routine use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure. We recommend more robust prospective studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods.

Suggestions for Practice

Several practice suggestions were developed based on the evidence from the literature. Due to the altered metabolism and excretion of sugammadex and rocuronium in patients with CRF, the utility of neuromuscular monitoring is essential in the proper management of neuromuscular blockade and antagonism. Neglecting neuromuscular monitoring may lead to under- or overdosage of sugammadex. Underdosing may result in residual neuromuscular blockade, which could potentially have harmful consequences for the patient. Overdosage can cause an excess amount of free plasma sugammadex, necessitating a higher dose of subsequent aminosteroidal NMBA to achieve the desired level of NMB (Kurita et al., 2016). Therefore, providers should adhere to the dosing guidelines specified by the manufacturer when administering sugammadex. Merck & Co., Inc. recommends administration of a 2 mg/kg dose if there is reappearance of T2 with TOF stimulation and a 4 mg/kg dose if there are no twitches upon TOF stimulation but 1 to 2 PTC present (Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp., 2015). Additionally, if the patient were to be hemodialyzed postoperatively, providers should ensure that a high-flux filter is being utilized since low-flux filters were not found to be effective in reducing the plasma concentration of sugammadex (Cammu et al., 2012; Kurita et al., 2016; Staals et al., 2010).

Conclusion

Sugammadex has been progressively establishing itself as the standard of practice for NMB antagonism. The current ASA guidelines on monitoring and antagonism of NMB make no reference to the use of sugammadex in patients with CRF, and the FDA does not currently advise its use in those with severe renal impairment. Nonetheless, instances of its application in patients with CRF have been noted in the clinical setting, along with corresponding case reports in the literature. As healthcare providers increasingly turn to the off-label use of sugammadex in individuals with CRF, it is imperative for them to stay informed about the latest research concerning its use in this population. A review of the literature suggests that sugammadex may be a safe and efficacious antagonist of rocuronium-induced NMB in adult patients with severe renal failure. However, more robust data with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are required to recommend its regular use in this population. Until more data is available, we suggest that providers administering sugammadex utilize neuromuscular monitoring, follow manufacturer dosing guidelines, and employ high-flux filters during HD to mitigate patient risks. A presentation and manuscript were developed to share the valuable insights and knowledge from this project. The dissemination of project findings holds the potential to educate providers and help them choose the most appropriate neuromuscular blocking and reversal agent for patients.

References

- Adams, D. R., Tollinche, L. E., Yeoh, C. B., Artman, J., Mehta, M., Phillips, D., Fischer, G. W., Quinlan, J. J., & Sakai, T. (2020). Short-term safety and effectiveness of sugammadex for surgical patients with end-stage renal disease: A two-centre retrospective study. *Anaesthesia*, 75(3), 348-352. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.14914>
- Altmetric. (n.d.). *The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. Overview of attention for article published in British Medical Journal, March 2021*. British Medical Journal. <https://bmj.altmetric.com/details/102933697/citations>
- Amneal Pharmaceuticals. (2020). *Neostigmine Methylsulfate Injection, USP*. <https://www.amneal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/NEOWS-03-Neostigmine-PI.pdf>
- Aragón-Benedí, C., Pascual-Bellosta, A., Ortega-Lucea, S., Visiedo-Sánchez, S., Martínez-Ubieto, J., & Research Group in Anaesthesia, Resuscitation, and Perioperative Medicine of Institute for Health Research Aragón. (2022). Predictive study of pharmacological reversal for residual neuromuscular blockade and postoperative pulmonary complications: A prospective, observational, cohort study. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 14955. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-18917-y>
- Arslantas, R., & Cevik, B. E. (2019). Retrospective investigation of grafted kidney function after reversal of neuromuscular blockade using neostigmine or sugammadex. *Transplant Proceedings*, 51(7), 2265-2267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2019.03.051>
- Bologheanu, R., Lichtenegger, P., Maleczek, M., Laxar, D., Schaden, E., & Kimbeger, O. (2022). A retrospective study of sugammadex for reversal of neuromuscular blockade induced by rocuronium in critically ill patients in the ICU. *Scientific Reports* 12, 897. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-04818-7>

- Bom, A., Bradley, M., Cameron, K., Clark, J. K., Van Egmond, J., Feilden, H., MacLean, E. J., Muir, A. W., Palin, R., Rees, D. C., & Zhang, M. Q. (2002). A novel concept of reversing neuromuscular block: chemical encapsulation of rocuronium bromide by a cyclodextrin-based synthetic host. *Angewandte Chemie (International ed. in English)*, 41(2), 266–270. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-3773\(20020118\)41:2<265::aid-anie265>3.0.co;2-q](https://doi.org/10.1002/1521-3773(20020118)41:2<265::aid-anie265>3.0.co;2-q)
- British Medical Journal. (2023, April). *Research methods & Reporting. The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews*. British Medical Journal. <https://www.bmj.com/content/372/bmj.n71/article-info>
- Cammu, G., Van Vlem, B., van den Heuvel, M., Stet, L., el Galta, R., Eloot, S., & Demeyer, I. (2012). Dialysability of sugammadex and its complex with rocuronium in intensive care patients with severe renal impairment. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 109(3), 382–390. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aes207>
- Carron, M., Andreatta, G., Pesenti, E., De Cassai, A., Feltracco, P., Linassi, F., Sergi, M., Di Bella, C., Di Bello, M., Neri, F., Silvestre, C., Furian, L., & Navalesi, P. (2022). Impact on grafted kidney function of rocuronium-sugammadex vs cisatracurium-neostigmine strategy for neuromuscular block management. An Italian single-center, 2014-2017 retrospective cohort case-control study. *Perioperative Medicine*, 11(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13741-021-00231-2>
- Cedborg, A. I., Sundman, E., Bodén, K., Hedström, H. W., Kuylenstierna, R., Ekberg, O., & Eriksson, L. I. (2014). Pharyngeal function and breathing pattern during partial neuromuscular block in the elderly: Effects on airway protection. *Anesthesiology*, 120(2), 312–325. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0000000000000043>

- Dang, D., Dearholt, S., Bissett, K., Ascenzi, J., & Whalen, M. (2022). *Johns Hopkins evidence-based practice for nurses and healthcare professionals: Model and guidelines* (4th ed.). Sigma Theta Tau International.
- Davies, O., Husain, T., & Stephens, R. C. M. (2017). Postoperative pulmonary complications following non-cardiothoracic surgery. *British Journal of Anesthesia Education*, 17(9), 295–300. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bjaed/mkx012>
- de Souza, C. M., Tardelli, M. A., Tedesco, H., Garcia, N. N., Caparros, M. P., Alvarez-Gomez, J. A., & de Oliveira Junior, I. S. (2015). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex in the reversal of deep neuromuscular blockade induced by rocuronium in patients with end-stage renal disease: A comparative prospective clinical trial. *European Journal of Anaesthesiology*, 32(10), 681–686. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EJA.0000000000000312>
- Doshu-Kajiura, A., Suzuki, J., & Suzuki, T. (2021). Prolonged onset and duration of action of rocuronium after accidental subcutaneous injection in a patient with chronic renal failure—a case report. *Journal of Anesthesia Clinical Reports*, 7(1), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-021-00421-3>
- Exela Pharma Sciences. (2018). *GLYRX-PF- glycopyrrolate injection, solution*. <https://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/fda/fdaDrugXsl.cfm?setid=2189f3f5-39dc-4e85-b7c6-9515ded59686&type=display>
- Fernandez-Bustamante, A., Frenzl, G., Sprung, J., Kor, D. J., Subramaniam, B., Martinez Ruiz, R., Lee, J. W., Henderson, W. G., Moss, A., Mehdiratta, N., Colwell, M. M., Bartels, K., Kolodzie, K., Giquel, J., & Vidal Melo, M. F. (2017). Postoperative pulmonary complications, early mortality, and hospital stay following noncardiothoracic surgery: A multicenter study by the perioperative research network investigators. *Journal of*

American Medical Association Surgery, 152(2), 157–166.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamasurg.2016.4065>

Fierro, C., Medoro, A., Mignogna, D., Porcile, C., Ciampi, S., Foderà, E., Flocco, R., Russo, C., & Martucci, G. (2021). Severe hypotension, bradycardia and asystole after sugammadex administration in an elderly patient. *Medicina*, 57(1), 79.

<https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57010079>

Fortier, L. P., McKeen, D., Turner, K., de Médicis, É., Warriner, B., Jones, P. M., Chaput, A., Pouliot, J. F., & Galarneau, A. (2015). The RECITE study: A Canadian prospective, multicenter study of the incidence and severity of residual neuromuscular blockade. *Anesthesia and Analgesia*, 121(2), 366–372.

<https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000000757>

Hristovska, A. M., Duch, P., Allingstrup, M., & Afshari, A. (2017). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex versus neostigmine in reversing neuromuscular blockade in adults. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, 8(8), CD012763.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012763>

Joshi, K. G., & Frierson, R. L. (2020). Off-label prescribing: How to limit your liability. *Current Psychiatry*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.12788/cp.0035>

Kanda, H., Hirasaki, Y., Iida, T., Kanao-Kanda, M., Toyama, Y., Chiba, T., & Kunisawa, T. (2017). Perioperative management of patients with end-stage renal disease. *Journal of Cardiothoracic and Vascular Anesthesia*, 31(6), 2251–2267.

<https://doi.org/10.1053/j.jvca.2017.04.019>

Kent, N. B., Liang, S. S., Phillips, S., Smith, N. A., Khandkar, C., Eikermann, M., & Stewart, P. A. (2018). Therapeutic doses of neostigmine, depolarising neuromuscular blockade and

- muscle weakness in awake volunteers: a double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomised volunteer study. *Anaesthesia*, 73, 1079-1089. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.14386>
- Kheterpal, S., Vaughn, M. T., Dubovoy, T. Z., Shah, N. J., Bash, L. D., Colquhoun, D. A., Shanks, A. M., Mathis, M. R., Soto, R. G., Bardia, A., Bartels, K., McCormick, P. J., Schonberger, R. B., & Saager, L. (2020). Sugammadex versus neostigmine for reversal of neuromuscular blockade and postoperative pulmonary complications (stronger): A multicenter matched cohort analysis. *Anesthesiology*, 132(6), 1371–1381. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ALN.0000000000003256>
- Kim, Y. S., Lim, B. G., Won, Y. J., Oh, S. K., Oh, J. S., & Cho, S. A. (2021). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex for the reversal of rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in patients with end-stage renal disease: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicina*, 57(11), 1259. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57111259>
- Kurita, S., Moriwaki, K., Shiroyama, K., Sanuki, M., Toyota, Y., & Takebayashi, M. (2016). Rocuronium-sugammadex use for electroconvulsive therapy in a hemodialysis patient: A case report. *Journal of Anesthesia Clinical Reports*, 2(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-016-0055-4>
- Lien, C. A. (2023). Neuromuscular blocking and reversal agents. In M. A. Gropper (Ed.), *Miller's anesthesia* (8th ed., pp. 160-184). Elsevier.
- Lobaz, S., Sammut, M., & Damodaran, A. (2013). Sugammadex rescue following prolonged rocuronium neuromuscular blockade with 'recurarisation' in a patient with severe renal failure. *British Medical Journal Case Reports*, 2013. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2012-007603>

- Luo, J., Chen, S., Min, S., & Peng, L. (2018). Reevaluation and update on efficacy and safety of neostigmine for reversal of neuromuscular blockade. *Therapeutics And Clinical Risk Management, 14*, 2397–2406. <https://doi.org/10.2147/TCRM.S179420>
- Merck & Co. (2023a, February). *Selected safety information for Bridion® (sugammadex)*. Merck Connect. <https://www.merckconnect.com/bridion/safety-information/>
- Merck & Co. (2023b, June). *US District Court for the District of New Jersey rules in favor of Merck in patent infringement lawsuit related to BRIDION® (sugammadex)*. <https://www.merck.com/news/u-s-district-court-for-the-district-of-new-jersey-rules-in-favor-of-merck-in-patent-infringement-lawsuit-related-to-bridion-sugammadex/>
- Merck Sharp & Dohme Corp. (2015). *Highlights of prescribing information*. Food and Drug Administration. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2015/0222251bl.pdf
- Min, K. C., Lasseter, K. C., Marbury, T. C., Wrishko, R. E., Hanley, W. D., Wolford, D. G., Udo de Haes, J., Reitmann, C., & Gutstein, D. E. (2017). Pharmacokinetics of sugammadex in subjects with moderate and severe renal impairment. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics, 55*(9), 746–752. <https://doi.org/10.5414/CP203025>
- Miyazaki, Y., Sunaga, H., Kida, K., Hobo, S., Inoue, N., Muto, M., & Uezono, S. (2018). Incidence of anaphylaxis associated with sugammadex. *Anesthesia and Analgesia, 126*(5), 1505–1508. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000002562>
- Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & The PRISMA Group. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *Public Library of Science Medicine, 6*(7), e1000097. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1000097>

- Murphy, G. S., Avram, M. J., Greenberg, S. B., Bilimoria, S., Benson, J., Maher, C. E., Teister, K. J., & Szokol, J. W. (2021). Neuromuscular and clinical recovery in thoracic surgical patients reversed with neostigmine or sugammadex. *Anesthesia and Analgesia*, 133(2), 435–444. <https://doi.org/10.1213/ANE.0000000000005294>
- Navare, S. R., Garcia Medina, O., Prielipp, R. C., & Weinkauff, J. L. (2019). Sugammadex reversal of a large subcutaneous depot of rocuronium in a dialysis patient: A case report. *Anesthesia & Analgesia Practice*, 12(10), 375–377. <https://doi.org/10.1213/XAA.0000000000000934>
- Ono, Y., Fujita, Y., Kajiura, T., Okawa, H., Nakashima, J., Isobe, H., & Fujiwara, Y. (2018). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex in patients undergoing renal transplantation. *Journal of Anesthesia Clinical Reports*, 4(1), 56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-018-0192-z>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021a). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *British Medical Journal*, 372, n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021b). The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *International Journal of Surgery*, 88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsu.2021.105906>

- Page, M. J., McKenzie, J. E., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... Moher, D. (2021c) The PRISMA 2020 statement: An updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *Public Library of Science Medicine*, 18(3).
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1003583>
- Page, M. J., Moher, D., Bossuyt, P. M., Boutron, I., Hoffmann, T. C., Mulrow, C. D., Shamseer, L., Tetzlaff, J. M., Akl, E. A., Brennan, S. E., Chou, R., Glanville, J., Grimshaw, J. M., Hróbjartsson, A., Lalu, M. M., Li, T., Loder, E. W., Mayo-Wilson, E., McDonald, S., ... McKenzie, J. E. (2021). PRISMA 2020 explanation and elaboration: Updated guidance and exemplars for reporting systematic reviews. *British Medical Journal*, 372, n160.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n160>
- Palamuthusingam, D., Nadarajah, A., Pascoe, E. M., Craig, J., Johnson, D. W., Hawley, C. M., & Fahim, M. (2020). Postoperative mortality in patients on chronic dialysis following elective surgery: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Public Library of Science One*, 15(6), e0234402. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0234402>
- Palamuthusingam, D., Nadarajah, A., Johnson, D. W., Pascoe, E. M., Hawley, C. M., & Fahim, M. (2021). Morbidity after elective surgery in patients on chronic dialysis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *BioMed Central Nephrology*, 22(1), 97.
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12882-021-02279-0>
- Panhuizen, I. F., Gold, S. J., Buerkle, C., Snoeck, M. M., Harper, N. J., Kaspers, M. J., van den Heuvel, M. W., & Hollmann, M. W. (2015). Efficacy, safety and pharmacokinetics of sugammadex 4 mg kg⁻¹ for reversal of deep neuromuscular blockade in patients with

severe renal impairment. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 114(5), 777–784.

<https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aet586>

Paredes, S., Porter, S. B., Porter, I. E., II, & Renew, J. R. (2020). Sugammadex use in patients with end-stage renal disease: A historical cohort study. Utilisation de sugammadex chez les patients atteints d'insuffisance rénale terminale : Une étude de cohorte historique.

Canadian Journal of Anaesthesia, 67(12), 1789–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12630-020-01812-3>

Pfaff, K., Tumin, D., & Tobias, J. D. (2019). Sugammadex for reversal of neuromuscular blockade in a patient with renal failure. *Journal of Pediatric Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 24(3), 238–241. <https://doi.org/10.5863/1551-6776-24.3.238>

Raval, A. D., Uyei, J., Karabis, A., Bash, L. D., & Brull, S. J. (2020). Incidence of residual neuromuscular blockade and use of neuromuscular blocking agents with or without antagonists: A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of Clinical Anesthesia*, 64, 109818.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinane.2020.109818>

Saager, L., Maiese, E. M., Bash, L. D., Meyer, T. A., Minkowitz, H., Groudine, S., Philip, B. K., Tanaka, P., Gan, T. J., Rodriguez-Blanco, Y., Soto, R., & Heisel, O. (2019). Incidence, risk factors, and consequences of residual neuromuscular block in the United States: The prospective, observational, multicenter RECITE-US study. *Journal of Clinical Anesthesia*, 55, 33–41.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinane.2018.12.042>

Song, S., Cho, H. B., Park, S. Y., Koo, W. M., Choi, S. J., Yoon, S., Park, S., Yoo, J. H., Kim, M. G., Chung, J. W., & Kim, S. H. (2022). Postoperative mortality in patients with end-stage renal disease according to the use of sugammadex: A single-center retrospective

- propensity score matched study. *Anesthesia and Pain Medicine*, 17(4), 371–380.
<https://doi.org/10.17085/apm.22189>
- Staals, L. M., Snoeck, M. M., Driessen, J. J., Flockton, E. A., Heeringa, M., & Hunter, J. M. (2008). Multicentre, parallel-group, comparative trial evaluating the efficacy and safety of sugammadex in patients with end-stage renal failure or normal renal function. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 101(4), 492–497. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aen216>
- Staals, L. M., Snoeck, M. M., Driessen, J. J., van Hamersvelt, H. W., Flockton, E. A., van den Heuvel, M. W., & Hunter, J. M. (2010). Reduced clearance of rocuronium and sugammadex in patients with severe to end-stage renal failure: A pharmacokinetic study. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 104(1), 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aep340>
- Sun, X., Zhou, X., Yu, Y., & Liu, H. (2018). Exploring reporting quality of systematic reviews and meta-analyses on nursing interventions in patients with Alzheimer’s disease before and after PRISMA introduction. *BioMed Central Medical Research Methodology*, 18(1), 154. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-018-0622-7>
- Tajaate, N., Schreiber, J. U., Fuchs-Buder, T., Jelting, Y., & Kranke, P. (2018). Neostigmine-based reversal of intermediate acting neuromuscular blocking agents to prevent postoperative residual paralysis: A systematic review. *European Journal of Anaesthesiology*, 35(3), 184–192. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EJA.0000000000000741>
- Tam, W. W. S., Lo, K. K. H., & Khalechelvam, P. (2017). Endorsement of PRISMA statement and quality of systematic reviews and meta-analyses published in nursing journals: A cross-sectional study. *British Medical Journal*, 7(2), e013905.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2016-013905>

- Tao, K. M., Li, X. Q., Zhou, Q. H., Moher, D., Ling, C. Q., & Yu, W. F. (2011). From QUOROM to PRISMA: A survey of high-impact medical journals' instructions to authors and a review of systematic reviews in anesthesia literature. *Public Library of Science One*, 6(11), e27611. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0027611>
- Thilen, S. R., Weigel, W. A., Todd, M. M., Dutton, R. P., Lien, C. A., Grant, S. A., Szokol, J. W., Eriksson, L. I., Yaster, M., Grant, M. D., Agarkar, M., Marbella, A. M., Blanck, J. F., & Domino, K. B. (2023). 2023 American Society of Anesthesiologists practice guidelines for monitoring and antagonism of neuromuscular blockade: A report by the American Society of Anesthesiologists task force on neuromuscular blockade. *Anesthesiology*, 138(1), 13-41. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aln.0000000000004379>
- U.S. Food & Drug Administration. (2018, February 5). Understanding unapproved use of approved drugs “off label.” <https://www.fda.gov/patients/learn-about-expanded-access-and-other-treatment-options/understanding-unapproved-use-approved-drugs-label>
- Vaidya, S. R., & Aeddula, N. R. (2022). *Chronic Renal Failure*. StatPearls Publishing. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK535404/>
- Van Norman, G. A. (2023). Off-label use vs off-label marketing of drugs: Part 1: Off-label use—patient harms and prescriber responsibilities. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology: Basic to Translational Science*, 8(2), 224–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacbts.2022.12.011>
- Vargas, M., Buonanno, P., Sica, A., Sabatella, E., D'Alessio, F. P., Alfieri, S., Iacovazzo, C., Carrano, R., & Servillo, G. (2021). Effects of sugammadex plus rocuronium vs neostigmine plus cisatracurium during renal transplantation on graft function: A

retrospective, case-control study. *Transplant Proceedings*, 53(3), 818-824.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2020.09.012>

Wittich, C. M., Burkle, C. M., & Lanier, W. L. (2012). Ten common questions (and their answers) about off-label drug use. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*, 87(10), 982–990.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2012.04.017>

Appendix A

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist item	Location where item is reported
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies. Specify the date when each source was last searched or consulted.	
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review, including how many reviewers screened each record and each report retrieved, whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report, whether they worked independently, any processes for obtaining or confirming data from study investigators, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought. Specify whether all results that were compatible with each outcome domain in each study were sought (e.g. for all measures, time points, analyses), and if not, the methods used to decide which results to collect.	
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought (e.g. participant and intervention characteristics, funding sources). Describe any assumptions made about any missing or unclear information.	
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies, including details of the tool(s) used, how many reviewers assessed each study and whether they worked independently, and if applicable, details of automation tools used in the process.	
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) (e.g. risk ratio, mean difference) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis (e.g. tabulating the study intervention characteristics and comparing against the planned groups for each synthesis (item #5)).	
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis, such as handling of missing summary statistics, or data conversions.	
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s). If meta-analysis was performed, describe the model(s), method(s) to identify the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity, and software package(s) used.	
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results (e.g. subgroup analysis, meta-regression).	
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis (arising from reporting biases).	
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for an outcome.	

PRISMA 2020 Checklist

Section and Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Location where item is reported
RESULTS			
Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process, from the number of records identified in the search to the number of studies included in the review, ideally using a flow diagram.	
	16b	Cite studies that might appear to meet the inclusion criteria, but which were excluded, and explain why they were excluded.	
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: (a) summary statistics for each group (where appropriate) and (b) an effect estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval), ideally using structured tables or plots.	
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted. If meta-analysis was done, present for each the summary estimate and its precision (e.g. confidence/credible interval) and measures of statistical heterogeneity. If comparing groups, describe the direction of the effect.	
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted to assess the robustness of the synthesized results.	
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results (arising from reporting biases) for each synthesis assessed.	
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	
DISCUSSION			
Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	
OTHER INFORMATION			
Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number, or state that the review was not registered.	
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed, or state that a protocol was not prepared.	
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review, and the role of the funders or sponsors in the review.	
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71

For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Appendix B

PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram for New Systematic Reviews

Figure 1

PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram for New Systematic Reviews

*Consider, if feasible to do so, reporting the number of records identified from each database or register searched (rather than the total number across all databases/registers).

**If automation tools were used, indicate how many records were excluded by a human and how many were excluded by automation tools.

From: Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* 2021;372:n71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.n71. For more information, visit: <http://www.prisma-statement.org/>

Appendix C

JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence

Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice Model for Nursing and Healthcare Professionals

Hierarchy of Evidence Guide Appendix D

Note: Refer to the appropriate Evidence Appraisal Tool (Research [Appendix E] or Nonresearch [Appendix F]) to determine quality ratings.

	Evidence Level	Types of Evidence
Research Evidence (Appendix E)	Level I	<input type="checkbox"/> Experimental study, randomized controlled trial (RCT) <input type="checkbox"/> Explanatory mixed methods design that includes only a Level I quantitative study <input type="checkbox"/> Systematic review of RCTs, with or without meta-analysis
	Level II	<input type="checkbox"/> Quasi-experimental study <input type="checkbox"/> Explanatory mixed methods design that includes only a Level II quantitative study <input type="checkbox"/> Systematic review of a combination of RCTs and quasi-experimental studies, or quasi-experimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis
	Level III	<input type="checkbox"/> Nonexperimental study <input type="checkbox"/> Systematic review of a combination of RCTs, quasi-experimental and nonexperimental studies, or nonexperimental studies only, with or without meta-analysis. <input type="checkbox"/> Exploratory, convergent, or multiphase mixed methods studies <input type="checkbox"/> Explanatory mixed methods design that includes only a Level III quantitative study <input type="checkbox"/> Qualitative study <input type="checkbox"/> Systematic review of qualitative studies with or without meta-synthesis
Nonresearch Evidence (Appendix F)	Level IV	Opinion of respected authorities and/or nationally recognized expert committees or consensus panels based on scientific evidence. Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical practice guidelines <input type="checkbox"/> Consensus panels/position statements
	Level V	Based on experiential and non-research evidence. Includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Scoping reviews <input type="checkbox"/> Integrative reviews <input type="checkbox"/> Literature reviews <input type="checkbox"/> Quality improvement, program or financial evaluation <input type="checkbox"/> Case reports <input type="checkbox"/> Opinion of nationally recognized expert(s) based on experiential evidence

Appendix D

JHEBP Research Evidence Appraisal Tools

Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice Model for Nursing and Healthcare Professionals

Research Evidence Appraisal Tool Appendix E

Does this evidence answer the EBP question?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes → Continue appraisal
		<input type="checkbox"/> No → STOP, do not continue evidence appraisal
Article Summary Information		
Article Title:		
Author(s):	Number:	
Population, size, and setting:	Publication date:	
Complete after appraisal		
Evidence level and quality rating:		
Study findings that help answer the EBP question:		
Article Appraisal Workflow		
Is this study:		
<input type="checkbox"/> QuaNtitative (collection, analysis, and reporting of numerical data) Numerical data (how many, how much, or how often) are used to formulate facts, uncover patterns, and generalize to a larger population; provide observed effects of a program, problem, or condition. Common methods are polls, surveys, observations, and reviews of records or documents. Data are analyzed using statistical tests. → For QuaNtitative leveling of a single research study go to Section IA → For QuaNtitative leveling of multiple research studies go to Section IB		
<input type="checkbox"/> QuaLitative (collection, analysis, and reporting of narrative data) Rich narrative data to gain a deep understanding of phenomena, meanings, perceptions, concepts, and experiences from those experiencing it. Sample sizes are relatively small and determined by the point of redundancy when no new information is gleaned, and key themes are reiterated (data saturation). Data are analyzed using thematic analysis. Often a starting point for studies when little research exists; may use results to design empirical studies. Common methods are focus groups, individual interviews (unstructured or semi-structured), and participation/observations. → For QuaLitative leveling of a single research study go to Section IIA → For QuaLitative leveling of multiple research studies go to Section IIB		
<input type="checkbox"/> Mixed methods (results reported both numerically and narratively) A study design (a single study or series of studies) that uses rigorous procedures in collecting and analyzing both quaNtitative and quaLitative data. <i>Note:</i> QuaNtitative survey designs with open-ended questions do not meet criteria for mixed methods research because those questions are not approached using strict quaLitative methods. Mixed methods studies provide a better understanding of research problems than using either a quaNtitative or quaLitative approach alone. → For Mixed Methods leveling of single and mixed studies review go to Section III		

Research Evidence Appraisal Tool
Appendix E

Section I: QuaNtitative Appraisal																																																																					
A	<p>Is this a report of a single research study? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes → Continue to decision tree <input type="checkbox"/> No → Go to Section I: B</p>																																																																				
Level	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 60%;"> <pre> graph TD Q1[Was there manipulation of an independent variable?] -- Yes --> Q2[Was there a control group?] Q1 -- No --> L3[Level III (Nonexperimental)] Q2 -- Yes --> Q3[Were study participants randomly assigned to the intervention and control groups?] Q2 -- No --> L2[Level II (Quasi-experimental)] Q3 -- Yes --> L1[Level I (Randomized Control Trial; RCT)] Q3 -- No --> L2 </pre> </div> <div style="width: 35%; padding-left: 20px;"> <p>Level I studies include randomized control trials (RCTs) or experimental studies</p> <p>Level II studies have some degree of investigator control and some manipulation of an independent variable but lack random assignment to groups and may not have a control group</p> <p>Level III studies lack manipulation of an independent variable; can be descriptive, comparative, or correlational; and often use secondary data</p> </div> </div>																																																																				
After determining the level of evidence, determine the quality of evidence using the considerations below:																																																																					
Quality	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Does the researcher identify what is known and not known about the problem?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Does the researcher identify how the study will address any gaps in knowledge?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Was the purpose of the study clearly presented?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Was the literature review current (most sources within the past five years or a seminal study)?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Was sample size sufficient based on study design and rationale?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">If there is a control group:</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Were the characteristics and/or demographics similar in both the control and intervention groups?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> If multiple settings were used, were the settings similar?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Were all groups equally treated except for the intervention group(s)?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Are data collection methods described clearly?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Were the instruments reliable (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.70$)?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Was instrument validity discussed?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">If surveys or questionnaires were used, was the response rate $\geq 25\%$?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Were the results presented clearly?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">If tables were presented, was the narrative consistent with the table content?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> N/A</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Were study limitations identified and addressed?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">Were conclusions based on results?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"><input type="checkbox"/> No</td> <td style="padding: 2px;"></td> </tr> </table>	Does the researcher identify what is known and not known about the problem?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		Does the researcher identify how the study will address any gaps in knowledge?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		Was the purpose of the study clearly presented?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		Was the literature review current (most sources within the past five years or a seminal study)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		Was sample size sufficient based on study design and rationale?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		If there is a control group:				<input type="checkbox"/> Were the characteristics and/or demographics similar in both the control and intervention groups?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	<input type="checkbox"/> If multiple settings were used, were the settings similar?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	<input type="checkbox"/> Were all groups equally treated except for the intervention group(s)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	Are data collection methods described clearly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		Were the instruments reliable (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.70$)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	Was instrument validity discussed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	If surveys or questionnaires were used, was the response rate $\geq 25\%$?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	Were the results presented clearly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		If tables were presented, was the narrative consistent with the table content?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A	Were study limitations identified and addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No		Were conclusions based on results?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
Does the researcher identify what is known and not known about the problem?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
Does the researcher identify how the study will address any gaps in knowledge?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
Was the purpose of the study clearly presented?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
Was the literature review current (most sources within the past five years or a seminal study)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
Was sample size sufficient based on study design and rationale?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
If there is a control group:																																																																					
<input type="checkbox"/> Were the characteristics and/or demographics similar in both the control and intervention groups?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
<input type="checkbox"/> If multiple settings were used, were the settings similar?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
<input type="checkbox"/> Were all groups equally treated except for the intervention group(s)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
Are data collection methods described clearly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
Were the instruments reliable (Cronbach's $\alpha \geq 0.70$)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
Was instrument validity discussed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
If surveys or questionnaires were used, was the response rate $\geq 25\%$?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
Were the results presented clearly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
If tables were presented, was the narrative consistent with the table content?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> N/A																																																																		
Were study limitations identified and addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			
Were conclusions based on results?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> No																																																																			

Research Evidence Appraisal Tool
Appendix E

Section I: QuaNtitative Appraisal (continued)	
Quality	Circle the appropriate quality rating below:
Quality	<p>A High quality: Consistent, generalizable results; sufficient sample size for the study design; adequate control; definitive conclusions; consistent recommendations based on comprehensive literature review that includes thorough reference to scientific evidence.</p> <p>B Good quality: Reasonably consistent results; sufficient sample size for the study design; some control; fairly definitive conclusions; reasonably consistent recommendations based on fairly comprehensive literature review that includes some reference to scientific evidence.</p> <p>C Low quality: Little evidence with inconsistent results; insufficient sample size for the study design; conclusions cannot be drawn.</p>
Record findings that help answer the EBP question on page 1	

Research Evidence Appraisal Tool
Appendix E

Section I: QuaNtitative Appraisal (continued)		
B	Is this a summary of multiple sources of research evidence?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes → Continue to decision tree <input type="checkbox"/> No → Use the Nonresearch Evidence Appraisal tool (Appendix F)
Level	<pre> graph TD Q1[Was there a comprehensive search strategy and rigorous appraisal method?] -- No --> N1[Go to the Nonresearch Evidence Appraisal Tool Appendix F] Q1 -- Yes --> Q2[Do the studies only include research evidence Levels I, II or III] Q2 -- No --> N1 Q2 -- Yes --> Q3[Are all studies included RCTs?] Q3 -- Yes --> L1[Level I] Q3 -- No --> Q4[Do the studies include qualitative or non-experimental research in addition to RCTs and/or quasi-experimental studies?] Q4 -- Yes --> L3[Level III] Q4 -- No --> L2[Level II] </pre>	
Quality	After determining level of evidence, determine the quality of evidence using the considerations below:	
	Were the variables of interest clearly identified?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Was the search comprehensive and reproducible? <input type="checkbox"/> Key terms stated <input type="checkbox"/> Multiple databases searched and identified <input type="checkbox"/> Inclusion and exclusion criteria stated	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Was there a flow diagram that included the number of studies eliminated at each level of review?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Were details of included studies presented (design, sample, methods, results, outcomes, strengths, and limitations)?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Were methods for appraising the strength of evidence (level and quality) described?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Were conclusions based on results? <input type="checkbox"/> Results were interpreted <input type="checkbox"/> Conclusions flowed logically from the research question, results, and interpretation	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Did the systematic review include a section addressing limitations and how they were addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No

Appendix E

JHEBP Nonresearched Evidence Appraisal Tools

Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice Model for Nursing and Healthcare Professionals

Nonresearch Evidence Appraisal Tool Appendix F

Does this evidence answer the EBP question?		<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Continue appraisal
		<input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> STOP, do not continue evidence appraisal
Article Summary Information		
Article Title:		
Author(s):	Number:	
Population, size, and setting:	Publication date:	
Complete after appraisal:		
Evidence level and quality rating:		
Study findings that help answer the EBP question:		
Article Appraisal Workflow		
Level	Is this evidence:	This is...
	<input type="checkbox"/> A clinical practice guideline or a consensus/position statement?	Level IV evidence, go to Section I: Level IV Appraisal to determine quality
	<input type="checkbox"/> A literature review or integrative review?	Level V evidence, go to Section II, A: Level V Appraisal to determine quality
	<input type="checkbox"/> An expert opinion?	Level V evidence, go to Section II, B: Level V Appraisal to determine quality
	<input type="checkbox"/> Case report?	Level V evidence, go to Section II, C: Level V Appraisal to determine quality
	<input type="checkbox"/> An organizational experience (including quality improvement, financial or program evaluations)?	Level V evidence, go to Section II, D: Level V Appraisal to determine quality
	<input type="checkbox"/> Community standard, clinician experience, or consumer preference?	Level V evidence, go to Section II, E: Level V Appraisal to determine quality

Nonresearch Evidence Appraisal Tool
Appendix F

Section II: Level V Quality Appraisal (continued)		
C Select the type of article:		
<input type="checkbox"/> Case report (an in-depth look at a person or group or another social unit)		
After selecting the type of Level V evidence, determine the quality of evidence using the considerations below:		
Quality	Is the purpose of the case report clearly stated?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Is the case report clearly presented?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Are the findings of the case report supported by relevant theory or research?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
	Are the recommendations clearly stated and linked to the findings?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
Circle the appropriate quality rating below:		
<p>A High quality: Expertise is clearly evident, draws definitive conclusions, and provides scientific rationale; thought leader in the field.</p> <p>B Good quality: Expertise appears to be credible, draws fairly definitive conclusions, and provides logical argument for opinions.</p> <p>C Low quality: Expertise is not discernable or is dubious; conclusions cannot be drawn.</p>		
Record findings that help answer the EBP question on page 1		

Appendix F

Figure 2: PRISMA Flow Diagram

Figure 2

PRISMA Flow Diagram

Note. The flow diagram shows the study search and selection process. Adapted from “The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews” by Page, McKenzie, et al., 2021a, British Medical Journal, 372, p. 5. Copyright 2020 by PRISMA Group. Adapted with permission.

Appendix G

Presentation for Anesthesia Providers

The Safety and Efficacy of Sugammadex in Patients with Chronic Renal Failure

Jillian Stasiun, BSN, RN

The slide features a large orange and white graphic on the left side, consisting of a semi-circle with a yellow sun-like shape and dashed lines, set against an orange background.

2023

ASA Practice Guidelines for Monitoring and Antagonism of Neuromuscular Blockade

ANESTHESIOLOGY
Trusted Evidence: Discovery to Practice®
2023 January

YES
NO

ACCESS NOW

The advertisement features a blue background with a hand holding a pulse oximeter on the right. On the left, there is a graphic of a journal cover for 'ANESTHESIOLOGY' with a brain scan image and 'YES' and 'NO' callouts. A red 'ACCESS NOW' button is located at the bottom right.

Stage of CKD	STAGE 1	STAGE 2	STAGE 3A	STAGE 3B	STAGE 4	STAGE 5
eGFR	90 or greater	Between 60 and 89	Between 45 and 59	Between 30 and 44	Between 15 and 29	Less than 15
Level of kidney damage	 End-stage kidney disease. Kidneys are close to failure or have completely failed. You will need to start dialysis or have a kidney transplant.					

Strength of Research

- 5 quasi-experimental studies
- 1 systematic review & meta-analysis of observational studies
- 2 retrospective cohort studies
- 5 retrospective case-controlled observational studies
- 6 case reports

Does it
work?

2.0 mg/kg dose for Moderate NMB (T2)

Mean recovery time:

- Severe renal failure: $2.0 \pm 0.72 \text{ min}^{18}$
- Normal renal function: $1.65 \pm 0.63 \text{ min}^{18}$

4.0 mg/kg dose Deep NMB (1-2 PTC)

Weighted mean difference:

- 1.14 [0.29 - 2.00] min^8

Is it safe?

Pharmacokinetics

↓ Renal function =

- ↓ Plasma clearance¹⁰
- ↑ Mean exposure, elimination $\frac{1}{2}$ life, mean resident time^{10, 18}

Detectability

- No sugammadex detected after 7 days¹⁰
- Rocuronium detected after 7 days but not after 28 days¹³

Dialysability

- HD w/high-flux filters:
 - 1st session: ↓ 69% sugammadex and ↓ 75% rocuronium³
 - Subsequent sessions: ↓ ~50%³

Safety

Recurarization

- No evidence of recurarization during postoperative period of 24-48 hours^{1, 7, 13, 17}

Adverse Events

- No significant difference in 30-day and 1-year mortality rates¹⁷
- No significant AEs^{3, 7, 13}
- Possible sugammadex-related AEs
 - pneumonia, hypoxemia, reintubation w/in 30 postop days¹⁴
 - extremity pain, dizziness, headache, and oral paresthesia¹⁰
 - diarrhea, nausea, anesthesia complications, headache, and decreased oxygen saturation¹⁷

Renal Transplants

Rocuronium-Sugammadex vs. Cisatracurium-Neostigmine

- No increased risk of AKI after transplantation²⁰
- Lower serum creatinine & urea levels 24 hrs post-transplant^{4,20}
- Lower incidences of postoperative severe hypoxemia & ICU admissions & shorter PACU stays⁴
- No AEs or signs of NMB recurrence 72 hrs post-transplant or at 6-month f/u^{2,12}
- No differences in rejection and 28-day mortality rates²

conclusion

It works!

No recurarization or major adverse events

Similar efficacy & safety during renal transplantation

Valuable option but not enough data to support recommended use

Suggestions for Practice

**USE NEUROMUSCULAR
MONITORING**

**DOSE ACCORDING TO
COMPANY GUIDELINES**

**USE HIGH-FLUX FILTERS
FOR HD**

References

- Adams, D. R., Tollinche, L. E., Yeoh, C. B., Artman, J., Mehta, M., Phillips, D., Fischer, G. W., Quinlan, J. J., & Sakai, T. (2020). Short-term safety and effectiveness of sugammadex for surgical patients with end-stage renal disease: A two-centre retrospective study. *Anaesthesia*, 75(3), 348-352. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.14914>
- Arsliantas, R., & Cevik, B. E. (2019). Retrospective investigation of grafted kidney function after reversal of neuromuscular blockade using neostigmine or sugammadex. *Transplant Proceedings*, 51(7), 2265-2267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2019.03.051>
- Cammu, G., Van Vlem, B., van den Heuvel, M., Stet, L., el Galta, R., Eloit, S., & Demeyer, I. (2012). Dialysability of sugammadex and its complex with rocuronium in intensive care patients with severe renal impairment. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 109(3), 382-390. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aez207>
- Carron, M., Andreatta, G., Pesenti, E., De Cassal, A., Feltracco, P., Linassi, F., Sergi, M., Di Bella, C., Di Bello, M., Neri, F., Silvestre, C., Furian, L., & Navalesi, P. (2022). Impact on grafted kidney function of rocuronium-sugammadex vs cisatracurium-neostigmine strategy for neuromuscular block management. An Italian single-center, 2014-2017 retrospective cohort case-control study. *Perioperative Medicine*, 11(1), 3.
- de Souza, C. M., Tardelli, M. A., Tedesco, H., Garcia, N. N., Caparros, M. P., Alvarez-Gomez, J. A., & de Oliveira Junior, I. S. (2015). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex in the reversal of deep neuromuscular blockade induced by rocuronium in patients with end-stage renal disease: A comparative prospective clinical trial. *European Journal of Anaesthesiology*, 32(10), 681-686. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EJA.0000000000000312>
- Doshu-Kajjura, A., Suzuki, J., & Suzuki, T. (2021). Prolonged onset and duration of action of rocuronium after accidental subcutaneous injection in a patient with chronic renal failure—a case report. *JA Clinical Reports*, 7(1), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-021-00421-3>
- Kim, Y. S., Lim, B. G., Won, Y. J., Oh, S. K., Oh, J. S., & Cho, S. A. (2021). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex for the reversal of rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in patients with end-stage renal disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicina*, 57(11), 1259. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57111259>
- Kurita, S., Moriwaki, K., Shiroyama, K., Sanuki, M., Toyota, Y., & Takebayashi, M. (2016). Rocuronium-sugammadex use for electroconvulsive therapy in a hemodialysis patient: A case report. *JA Clinical Reports*, 2(1), 28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-016-0055-4>
- Lobaz, S., Sammut, M., & Damodaran, A. (2013). Sugammadex rescue following prolonged rocuronium neuromuscular blockade with 'recurrarisation' in a patient with severe renal failure. *BMJ Case Reports*, 2013, bcr2012007603. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2012-007603>

10. Min, K. C., Lasseeter, K. C., Marbury, T. C., Wrishko, R. E., Hanley, W. D., Wolford, D. G., Udo de Haes, J., Reitmman, C., & Gutstein, D. E. (2017). Pharmacokinetics of sugammadex in subjects with moderate and severe renal impairment. *International Journal of Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 55(9), 746–752. <https://doi.org/10.5414/CP203025>
11. Navare, S. R., Garcia Medina, O., Prielipp, R. C., & Weinkauff, J. L. (2019). Sugammadex reversal of a large subcutaneous depot of rocuronium in a dialysis patient: A case report. *A&A Practice*, 12(10), 375–377. <https://doi.org/10.1213/XAA.0000000000000934>
12. Ono, Y., Fujita, Y., Kajiwara, T., Okawa, H., Nakashima, J., Isobe, H., & Fujiwara, Y. (2018). Efficacy and safety of sugammadex in patients undergoing renal transplantation. *JA Clinical Reports*, 4(1), 56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-018-0192-z>
13. Panhuizen, I. F., Gold, S. J., Buerkle, C., Snoeck, M. M., Harper, N. J., Kaspers, M. J., van den Heuvel, M. W., & Hollmann, M. W. (2015). Efficacy, safety and pharmacokinetics of sugammadex 4 mg kg⁻¹ for reversal of deep neuromuscular blockade in patients with severe renal impairment. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 114(5), 777–784. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aet586>
14. Paredes, S., Porter, S. B., Porter, I. E., 2nd, & Renew, J. R. (2020). Sugammadex use in patients with end-stage renal disease: a historical cohort study. Utilisation de sugammadex chez les patients atteints d'insuffisance rénale terminale : une étude de cohorte historique. *Canadian Journal of Anaesthesia*, 67(12), 1789–1797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12630-020-01812-3>
15. Pfaff, K., Tumin, D., & Tobias, J. D. (2019). Sugammadex for reversal of neuromuscular blockade in a patient with renal failure. *The Journal of Pediatric Pharmacology and Therapeutics*, 24(3), 238–241. <https://doi.org/10.5863/1551-6776-24.3.238>
16. Song, S., Cho, H. B., Park, S. Y., Koo, W. M., Chol, S. J., Yoon, S., Park, S., Yoo, J. H., Kim, M. G., Chung, J. W., & Kim, S. H. (2022). Postoperative mortality in patients with end-stage renal disease according to the use of sugammadex: a single-center retrospective propensity score matched study. *Anesthesia and Pain Medicine*, 17(4), 371–380. <https://doi.org/10.17085/apm.22189>
17. Staals, L. M., Snoeck, M. M., Driessen, J. J., Flockton, E. A., Heeringa, M., & Hunter, J. M. (2008). Multicentre, parallel-group, comparative trial evaluating the efficacy and safety of sugammadex in patients with end-stage renal failure or normal renal function. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 101(4), 492–497. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aen216>
18. Staals, L. M., Snoeck, M. M., Driessen, J. J., van Hamersvelt, H. W., Flockton, E. A., van den Heuvel, M. W., & Hunter, J. M. (2010). Reduced clearance of rocuronium and sugammadex in patients with severe to end-stage renal failure: a pharmacokinetic study. *British Journal of Anaesthesia*, 104(1), 31–39. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aep340>
19. Thilen, S. R., Weigel, W. A., Todd, M. M., Dutton, R. P., Lien, C. A., Grant, S. A., Szokol, J. W., Eriksson, L. I., Yaster, M., Grant, M. D., Agarkar, M., Marbella, A. M., Blanck, J. F., & Domino, K. B. (2023). 2023 American Society of Anesthesiologists practice guidelines for monitoring and antagonism of neuromuscular blockade: A report by the American Society of Anesthesiologists task force on neuromuscular blockade. *Anesthesiology*, 138(1), 13–41. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ain.0000000000004379>
20. Vargas, M., Buonanno, P., Sica, A., Sabatella, E., D'Alessio, F. P., Alfieri, S., Iacovazzo, C., Carrano, R., & Servillo, G. (2021). Effects of sugammadex plus rocuronium vs neostigmine plus cisatracurium during renal transplantation on graft function: A retrospective, case-control study. *Transplant Proceedings*, 53(3), 818–824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2020.09.012>

Appendix H

AANA Journal Manuscript

1

A Comprehensive Review of the Safety and Efficacy of Sugammadex in Patients with Chronic
Renal Failure

Jillian Stasiun, BSN, RN

School of Nursing, California State University, Fullerton, Fullerton, California

Sass Elisha, EdD, CRNA, FAAN

Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia, Pasadena, California

Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN

School of Nursing, California State University, Fullerton, Fullerton, California

Principal Author: Jillian Stasiun, BSN, RN, is a DNP Nurse Anesthesia student at Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia (KPSA) in Pasadena, California, and California State University, Fullerton (CSUF).

Sass Elisha, EdD, CRNA, FAAN, is an educator, anesthesia practitioner, and Assistant Director at KPSA.

Penny Weismuller, DrPH, RN, is a Professor and the Director of the School of Nursing at CSUF.

Corresponding Author:

Jillian Stasiun, BSN, RN

Email: jstasiun@csu.fullerton.edu

Abstract

Despite the absence of FDA approval, the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure ($\text{CrCl} < 30 \text{ ml/min}$) is observed in the clinical setting. This review utilized PubMed, Cochrane, and CINAHL databases to examine literature regarding the efficacy and safety of sugammadex as a reversal agent for rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade (NMB) in adults with chronic renal failure. Nineteen articles were identified – six quasi-experimental studies, one systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies, two retrospective cohort studies, four retrospective case-controlled studies, and six case reports. Plasma clearance of sugammadex was significantly lower in those with severe renal failure when compared to those with normal renal function. Sugammadex and its complex with rocuronium were found to be dialyzable when utilizing high-flux filters. Time to full reversal from moderate and deep levels of blockade was slightly prolonged. No incidences of recurarization or major adverse events were reported. Sugammadex may be a safe and effective reverse agent for rocuronium-induced NMB in adult patients with severe renal failure undergoing general and renal transplantation surgery. However, insufficient data is available to recommend its regular use in this patient population. More robust prospective studies with larger sample sizes and a longer follow-up period are warranted.

Key Words: *chronic renal failure, end-stage renal disease, sugammadex*

Background

Sugammadex has been progressively establishing itself as the standard of practice for neuromuscular blockade (NMB) antagonism. It is a modified gamma cyclodextrin that reverses NMB by encapsulating and binding aminosteroidal neuromuscular blocking agents (NMBA).^{1,2} Once encapsulated, the NMBA is inactive and unavailable to bind to nicotinic acetylcholine receptors at the neuromuscular junction, thus restoring normal neuromuscular transmission.¹ When compared to neostigmine, sugammadex has been shown to reverse all depths of NMB, reach full blockade recovery faster, and decrease rates of residual NMB and postoperative adverse events (e.g., bradycardia, PONV, desaturation, need for supplementary oxygen).^{2,3}

Current American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) guidelines recommend the use of sugammadex over neostigmine for shallow, moderate, and deep blockade to avoid residual NMB.¹ However, the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) advises caution against administering sugammadex to patients with severe renal impairment (creatinine clearance [CrCl] < 30 ml/min).¹ This caution stems from the fact that both sugammadex and its complex with the NMBA are predominately eliminated through renal excretion.¹ This results in a prolonged half-life of sugammadex in individuals with compromised renal function and potential consequences of its extended exposure.¹

Despite the regulatory caution, the landscape of clinical practice has seen instances where sugammadex has been employed in patients with severe renal failure. This deviation from formal recommendations has been documented in various clinical reports,⁴⁻⁹ shedding light on the nuanced decisions made in real-world medical scenarios. Due to the complexity of chronic renal failure and the advantages of sugammadex, situations arise where sugammadex may be the safest option for the patient (e.g., cannot ventilate, cannot intubate situations). Considering the benefits

of sugammadex, more research needs to be conducted to compile what is currently known about the use of sugammadex in patients with CFR.

The purpose of this review is to examine literature regarding the efficacy and safety of sugammadex as a reversal agent for rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in adults with chronic renal failure. This review aims to generate evidence-based suggestions that will guide providers in selecting the most appropriate neuromuscular blocking and reversal agent for patients with chronic renal failure.

Review of Literature

Methods

The literature review was conducted using PubMed, Cochrane, and CINAHL research databases. Combinations of the following keywords were used in the search: "sugammadex," "renal failure," "kidney failure," "chronic renal failure," "chronic kidney disease," "kidney disease," "end-stage renal disease," and "renal impairment." Inclusion criteria included full-text articles published within the last ten years, written in English, and pertained to the use of sugammadex in patients with renal disease. This timeframe was selected because it allowed for the inclusion of research conducted after FDA approval of sugammadex in 2015.¹ Due to the pharmacokinetic impact of age, pregnancy, and species, articles on pediatrics, parturients, and animal models were excluded. Studies that included vecuronium-induced blockade were also excluded as it was not the focus of this review. The identified articles were reviewed and examined individually for evidence related to the pharmacokinetics, safety, and efficacy of sugammadex as a reversal of rocuronium-induced NMB in patients with chronic renal failure. Citation chaining was also performed to identify key authors and publications relevant to this review's purpose.

Study Selection

The inclusion of studies in the review was based on predefined eligibility criteria and determined by one reviewer using a two-step process. All publications were first screened by title and abstract. Those that met the criteria then underwent a complete review of the text. Most studies were published within the predefined time restriction. However, citation chaining resulted in the procurement of three seminal articles published outside the 10-year time frame.¹⁰⁻¹²

Quality Assessment of Research Evidence

The quality and reliability of evidence were evaluated using the Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice (JHEBP) Model and Tools.¹³ The level of evidence for each article was categorized using the JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence Guide.¹³ Levels I and II on the hierarchy include experimental study designs (randomized control trials, systematic reviews, experimental, quasi-experimental) and are considered the strongest types of evidence. Non-experimental research, such as observational and qualitative studies, are considered Level III evidence. Level IV includes scientifically based clinical practice guidelines and position statements published by nationally recognized expert committees or consensus panels. Experiential and non-research evidence, such as case reports and various types of literature reviews, are the lowest types of evidence and fall under Level V. After categorization of evidence, the quality was determined using the JHEBP Evidence Appraisal Tools, resulting in the assignment of high, good, or low quality ratings.¹³

Ethical Considerations

The project proposal was evaluated by a designated reviewer on the Kaiser Permanente Southern California Institutional Review Board (IRB). It was determined that the literature

review is not considered human subjects research as defined by 45 CFR 46.102 e (1) and (l) and is therefore exempt from IRB approval.

Results

Identification of Studies

The electronic database search yielded 46 articles with duplicates removed. All 46 article titles and abstracts were screened for inclusion. After 29 articles were excluded, full texts of the remaining 17 articles were assessed for eligibility. Three articles were removed after full-text screening, resulting in a total of 14 articles that met the eligibility criteria from the database search. Additionally, five articles were identified from citation chaining, assessed, met criteria, and therefore included. Overall, a total of 19 articles were included in the literature review.

Quality Assessment

Most of the evidence collected was Level III and V on the JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence.¹³ Of the 19 articles, there were six quasi-experimental studies (Level II), one systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies (Level III), two retrospective cohort studies (Level III), four retrospective case-controlled observational studies (Level III), and six case reports (Level V).

Half of the case reports were found to be "high quality" evidence⁴⁻⁶, while the other half met the "good quality" criteria⁷⁻⁹. In those considered "high quality," the purpose of the case report was clearly stated, the report was clearly presented, the findings were supported by relevant research, and the recommendations were clearly stated and linked to the findings.⁴⁻⁶ The case reports considered "good quality" did not have clear recommendations.⁷⁻⁹

Three retrospective case-controlled studies investigated the impact of sugammadex on post-renal transplant recovery outcomes.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ While Carron et al¹⁵ was deemed "high quality," the

other two were categorized as "good quality" due to their reliance on older studies in their literature reviews and a lack of rationale for their chosen sample sizes.^{14,16} The last retrospective case-controlled study looked at mortality rates after the use of sugammadex in patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD).¹⁷ Upon assessment, it was considered "good quality" instead of "high quality" due to the use of older studies¹⁷.

Both retrospective cohort studies examined specific clinical outcomes as indicators of the safety profile of sugammadex in patients with ESRD.^{18,19} Paredes et al¹⁹ was categorized as "high quality" because there was a clear presentation of the problem, gaps in knowledge, study's purpose, data collection methods, and results. The authors also utilized current sources, justified sample size, discussed limitations, and made conclusions based on results.¹⁹ Adams et al.¹⁸ included older sources in their literature review but had many positive aspects that made the evidence "good quality." The systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies met "high quality" criteria with its well-defined topic, clear search method, thorough evaluation and synthesis of the literature, appropriate recommendations, and definitive conclusions.²⁰

The prospective studies examined in this review were considered quasi-experimental due to the absence of either a control group or randomization among study participants.^{10, 12,13, 21-23} All quasi-experimental studies met the criteria for "good quality" except for one.¹⁰ Cammu et al¹⁰ was found to be "poor quality" because of its limited sample of six participants, reducing their findings' external validity.

Study Participants' Level of Chronic Renal Failure

While the literature search did not limit the degree of renal impairment in individuals with chronic renal failure, the resultant literature evidence focused on adult patients with severe (CrCl <30 ml/min) or end-stage renal failure (CrCl <15 ml/min). Only Min et al²² included

patients with moderate renal failure (CrCl 30 to 50 ml/min) in addition to those with severe disease. Some study participants required some form of dialysis (hemodialysis or peritoneal) due to the severity of their disease, but it was not a requirement in all studies.

Within the literature evidence, several terms have been utilized interchangeably to describe the same degree of renal impairment. The terms "severe renal impairment," "severe renal failure," and "severe renal insufficiency" have all been used to describe participants with a CrCl <30 ml/min. Articles employing the terms "end-stage renal failure" or "end-stage renal disease" did not provide an associated creatinine clearance or glomerular filtration rate (GFR). However, these terms, along with "chronic kidney disease stage 5," are commonly associated with the staging of chronic kidney disease from the National Kidney Foundation, which defines ESRD as a GFR < 15ml/min.²⁴

Variables and Measures

The studies' key variables and measures encompassed various aspects of efficacy and safety, such as the time required to achieve complete NMB reversal, NMB recurrence, adverse events (AEs), mortality, postoperative respiratory complications, and renal function laboratory tests. Several studies also measured pharmacokinetic factors, specifically plasma and urine concentrations of rocuronium and sugammadex, area under the curve (AUC), elimination half-life, and mean residence time.

Findings

Efficacy

Numerous studies have investigated the effectiveness of sugammadex as a reversal agent for moderate and deep levels of rocuronium-induced NMB in patients with severe renal failure.^{11,20,21,23} In a multicenter prospective clinical trial conducted by Staals et al,¹¹ a 2.0 mg/kg

dose of sugammadex was utilized to reverse moderate depths of NMB (reappearance of the second TOF twitch or T2). Researchers found that patients with severe renal failure took longer to fully recover ($\text{TOFr} \geq 0.9$) than those with normal renal function, with a mean recovery time of 2.0 ± 0.72 minutes and 1.65 ± 0.63 minutes, respectively. However, the difference between the two groups was not statistically significant.¹¹ Two comparative studies that examined the reversal of deep NMB (1-2 post-tetanic count) using 4.0 mg/kg of sugammadex also found a prolonged time to full recovery in patients with severe renal failure.^{21,23} Panhuizen et al²³ observed a median [95% confidence interval] time to full recovery at 3.1 [2.4 - 4.6] minutes in the renal failure group and 1.9 [1.6 - 2.8] minutes in the control group. Similarly, de Souza et al²¹ reported a mean time to full recovery of 5.6 ± 3.6 minutes in the ESRD group and 2.7 ± 1.3 minutes in the control group. A systematic review and meta-analysis of six prospective case-control studies reported a weighted mean difference of 1.14 [0.29 - 2.00] minutes in time to $\text{TOFr} \geq 0.9$ between patients with ESRD and patients with normal renal function.²⁰ Despite these delays in recovery time, all four studies concluded that sugammadex could rapidly and reliably reverse NMB in patients with severe renal failure.^{11,20,21,23}

Sugammadex's effectiveness in reversing NMB among patients with severe renal failure has been documented across various clinical settings through case reports.⁴⁻⁹ Two case reports described patients with ESRD who experienced progressive NMB due to the inadvertent subcutaneous administration of rocuronium through an infiltrated peripheral intravenous catheter during induction.^{4,7} In these cases, administration of sugammadex at the end of surgery led to the cessation of the progression of NMB and complete recovery.^{4,7} Lobaz et al⁶ reported a case where sugammadex was successfully utilized as a rescue agent after the initial reversal with neostigmine led to postoperative recurarization. A retrospective observational study described

similar reports of using sugammadex as a rescue drug for inadequate reversal with neostigmine.¹⁸ Overall, the case reports illustrate sugammadex as a valuable option for managing NMB in patients with severe renal failure, especially in cases where neostigmine has proven ineffective or unsuitable.^{4,6,7,9}

Pharmacokinetics

Pharmacokinetic (PK) studies of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure have demonstrated significant changes in the drug's metabolism and clearance.^{12,22} Studies found a correlation between creatinine clearance and sugammadex clearance, such that as renal function declines, plasma clearance of sugammadex decreases. With decreased plasma clearance, patients with severe renal failure exhibited increased PK parameters that suggest prolonged exposure to sugammadex. More specifically, Staals et al¹² reported a 15-20-fold increase in the area under the curve (AUC), elimination half-life, and mean residence time, and a 17-fold decrease in the creatinine clearance of sugammadex. Despite a decreased clearance, plasma concentrations of sugammadex were undetectable after seven days post-dose in those with severe renal failure.²²

The impact of severe renal failure on the pharmacokinetics of rocuronium was similar to that of sugammadex, although less pronounced.¹² When comparing the plasma clearance of sugammadex and rocuronium in patients with ESRD, sugammadex had a slower mean total plasma clearance (5.5 ml/min) than rocuronium (41.8 ml/min) due to rocuronium's extra-renal means of metabolism and excretion¹². As a result, sugammadex plasma concentrations may remain elevated in those with ESRD during the postoperative period, thereby reducing the probability of unbound rocuronium.²⁰

In the PK analysis conducted by Panhuizen et al,²³ a group of 34 patients with severe renal failure who received sugammadex to reverse rocuronium-induced NMB was compared to a

control group of 33 patients with normal renal function. Plasma concentrations of both drugs were measured at various time intervals. Among the participants with severe renal failure, measurable concentrations of rocuronium were observed in six individuals seven days after administration, but no detectable concentrations were found on Day 28. The presence of sugammadex alongside rocuronium was not reported, as the PK analysis of sugammadex conducted by the same researchers was deemed invalid due to its failure to meet the quality standards set by Merck & Co., Inc. Nonetheless, considering the PK findings in Staals et al¹², sugammadex may also be present seven days post-dose, which contrasts with the findings reported in Min et al.²²

Dialysability

Several studies have explored the dialysability of sugammadex and the sugammadex-rocuronium complex, including two clinical trials and one case report.^{5,10,12} In a prospective clinical trial by Staals et al,¹² low-flux hemodialysis (HD) was not found to reduce the plasma concentration of sugammadex significantly. However, high-flux HD, which uses a more permeable filter, was more effective.¹⁰ In a single-center, open-label trial, six ICU patients with severe renal failure were dialyzed with a high-flux filter after 4.0 mg/kg of sugammadex was administered to reverse 0.6 mg/kg of rocuronium.¹⁰ Researchers reported a 69% reduction in sugammadex and a 75% reduction in rocuronium after the first dialysis session, and approximately a 50% reduction in subsequent sessions.¹⁰

A case report by Kurita et al⁵ demonstrated similar reduction ratios in an HD patient who received rocuronium and sugammadex for electroconvulsive therapy (ECT). The patient received a 0.6 mg/kg dose of rocuronium followed by 2.0 mg/kg of sugammadex for each bi-weekly ECT session. Between ECT sessions, she underwent high-flux HD that resulted in an average

reduction of 61.9% of sugammadex and its complex with rocuronium, consistent with the findings of Cammu et al.¹⁰ Despite having HD three times a week, the frequency at which she received sugammadex resulted in an accumulation of free sugammadex that led to a slight reduction in the efficacy of rocuronium during ECT sessions six through eight. While it is uncommon for patients on HD to receive sugammadex regularly, this case report emphasizes the importance of diligent NM monitoring and appropriate dosing in this patient population.

Safety

Given the potential safety concerns associated with the prolonged exposure of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure, researchers have examined the incidence of sugammadex-related AEs and recurarization.^{10,11,19,20,22,23} Three studies monitored the presence of recurrent NMB or recurarization after achieving full recovery with sugammadex.^{11,18,23} None of these studies found evidence of recurarization during the postoperative period of 24 to 48 hours in patients with severe renal failure.^{11,18,23} These findings were corroborated by a systematic review and meta-analysis that reported no difference in the incidence of NMB recurrence between patients with ESRD and those with normal renal function.²⁰ However, acceleromyography-determined recurarization in a control patient with normal renal function was noted in a study by Panhuizen et al.²³ It was suggested that an insufficient dose of sugammadex (4 mg/kg) given only five minutes after an intubating dose of rocuronium may have been responsible for the recurrence, and a higher dose (16 mg/kg) during the onset of NMB may have been more appropriate.²³

The incidence of AEs in patients with severe renal disease who received sugammadex varied across the studies. Cammu et al,¹⁰ Kim et al,²⁰ and Panhuizen et al²³ reported no significant AEs related to sugammadex administration in patients with severe renal failure.

Additionally, a retrospective propensity score-matched study by Song et al¹⁷ found no significant difference in 30-day and 1-year mortality rates in ESRD patients who received sugammadex compared to those who did not. However, three studies reported possible sugammadex-related AEs in patients with ESRD.^{11,19,22} Paredes et al¹⁹ found that among 219 ESRD patients who received sugammadex, 18 experienced pulmonary complications such as pneumonia, hypoxemia, and reintubation within 30 postoperative days. Although the authors did not believe these complications were likely related to NMB management, they could not completely rule out the possibility of sugammadex contributing to the AEs for six patients due to the absence of quantitative NM monitoring. In Min et al²², four patients with severe renal failure experienced possible sugammadex-related AEs such as extremity pain, dizziness, headache, and oral paresthesia. Staals et al¹¹ reported a total of eight AEs, occurring within 48 hours postoperatively, that could have been associated with sugammadex in five patients, two of whom were in the renally impaired group and three were in the control group. These AEs included diarrhea, nausea, anesthesia complications, headache, and decreased oxygen saturation. While no serious sugammadex-related AEs were observed in patients with severe renal failure, most researchers felt that there was insufficient data on the safety profile of sugammadex to support the recommended use of sugammadex as a reversal agent for this patient population.

Renal Transplant

The use of sugammadex as a reversal agent after renal transplant surgery poses additional concerns surrounding its impact on grafted kidney function. Three retrospective case-control cohort studies compared grafted kidney function in patients who received sugammadex versus those who received neostigmine.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ While rocuronium was the main NMBA utilized in Arslantas and Cervik¹⁴, Carron et al¹⁵ and Vargas et al¹⁶ compared the rocuronium-sugammadex

and cisatracurium-neostigmine strategies. These studies reviewed laboratory measures such as serum urea and creatinine, serum and urinary electrolytes, and estimated glomerular filtration rate, as well as AEs including acute rejection episodes, graft failure, hospital and post-anesthesia care unit length of stay, postoperative ICU admission, and NMB recurrence.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ Researchers reported lower serum creatinine and urea levels in the sugammadex group than in the neostigmine group during the initial 24 hours post-transplantation.^{15,16} In patients with ESRD, the use of sugammadex did not appear to increase the risk of acute kidney injury after transplantation.¹⁶ Additionally, the sugammadex group exhibited lower incidences of postoperative severe hypoxemia and ICU admissions and shorter post-anesthesia care unit stays.¹⁵ In a case series of 99 patients, no AEs or signs of NMB recurrence were observed in the first 72 hours post-transplantation or at a six-month follow-up.⁸ These results were consistent with those reported by Arslantas and Cervik,¹⁴ where no serious AEs were observed, and there were no differences in rejection and 28-day mortality rates between the sugammadex and neostigmine groups. Overall, the studies suggest that sugammadex may be safe and effective during renal transplantation, but the generalizability of their findings in the clinical setting may be limited.

Discussion

While neostigmine is currently the prevailing choice for reversing rocuronium-induced NMB in patients with chronic renal failure, it has limitations and potential side effects that can lead to adverse consequences for this patient population. In contrast, sugammadex has demonstrated greater efficiency and effectiveness as a reversal agent when compared to neostigmine.^{2,3} However, its use is not currently recommended in patients with severe renal failure due to limited safety data¹. Nevertheless, several case reports have documented its

utilization in various clinical scenarios within this population.⁴⁻⁹ To better understand the safety and efficacy of sugammadex in patients with chronic renal failure, further exploration of the current literature was warranted.

The literature search on the utilization of sugammadex in patients with severe renal failure revealed a scarcity of robust research on the subject. Among the limited articles that met the predefined eligibility criteria, the majority provided mid to low levels of evidence. Notably, no randomized controlled trials were found. Nevertheless, despite the lower levels of evidence, articles evaluating the same measures yielded consistent results. Studies investigating the efficacy of sugammadex have determined it to be effective in reversing moderate and deep levels of rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in patients with severe renal failure.^{11,20,21,23} Pharmacokinetic studies have shown that sugammadex clearance decreases as renal function declines, resulting in prolonged exposure to the drug.^{12,22} The exact timeframe for when sugammadex plasma concentrations become undetectable is still unclear, possibly falling between seven and 28 days post-dose.²³ Additionally, there is evidence that high-flux HD effectively reduces sugammadex plasma concentrations.^{5,10,12} Despite prolonged exposure, there was no evidence of significant AEs or recurarization. When sugammadex was used during renal transplantation, comparable efficacy and safety outcomes were obtained.^{8,14-16,21} All in all, sugammadex may be a valuable option for reversing NMB in patients with severe renal failure, but not enough data is available to support the recommended use of sugammadex in this population.

Off-Label Drug Use

Given that the FDA does not currently recommend the use of sugammadex in patients with severe renal impairment (CrCl <30 ml/min), using it in this population would fall under off-

label drug use (OLDU). Off-label drug use involves the prescription or administration of a medication in a manner not approved by the FDA.²⁵ However, it is important to note that the absence of FDA approval does not make its use illegal.²⁶ Since the FDA does not regulate the practice of medicine, the decision to prescribe or administer an unapproved drug ultimately lies within the discretion of the healthcare provider.²⁵ Anesthesia providers frequently engage in this commonplace and legally accepted practice, such as administering dexamethasone or propofol to prevent postoperative nausea.²⁷ However, it is an ethical and professional duty for healthcare providers to prioritize the patient's best interests and ground their OLDU decision in strong scientific evidence or medical opinion.²⁶

Enhancing patient safety and minimizing liability in OLDU requires providers to possess an in-depth understanding of both the medication and the patient.²⁵⁻²⁸ This comprehensive knowledge should include an understanding of the drug's pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics and the latest research from reliable sources.^{26,28} Additionally, providers should be able to provide a scientific or clinical rationale for why the chosen off-label drug is the most suitable option for their patient at that specific moment.^{26,28} Some sources recommend obtaining informed consent from the patient before OLDU, but it is not legally required.^{26,28} Lastly, there should be scrupulous documentation of the clinical assessment, rationale, consent (if obtained), and any adverse events that may have occurred.^{26,28}

Suggestions for Practice

Several practice suggestions were developed based on the evidence from the literature. Due to the altered metabolism and excretion of sugammadex and rocuronium in patients with CRF, the utility of neuromuscular monitoring is essential in the proper management of neuromuscular blockade and antagonism. Neglecting neuromuscular monitoring may lead to

under- or overdosage of sugammadex. Underdosing may result in residual neuromuscular blockade, which could potentially have harmful consequences for the patient. Overdosage can cause an excess amount of free plasma sugammadex, necessitating a higher dose of subsequent aminosteroidal NMBA to achieve the desired level of NMB. Therefore, providers should adhere to the dosing guidelines specified by the manufacturer when administering sugammadex. Merck & Co., Inc. recommends administration of a 2 mg/kg dose if there is reappearance of T2 with TOF stimulation and a 4 mg/kg dose if there are no twitches upon TOF stimulation but 1 to 2 PTC present¹. Additionally, if the patient were to be hemodialyzed postoperatively, providers should ensure that a high-flux filter is being utilized since low-flux filters were not effective in reducing the plasma concentration of sugammadex.^{5,10,12}

Strengths & Limitations

A limitation of this review is the scarcity of robust data. The majority of the articles were Level III and IV on the JHEBP Hierarchy of Evidence.¹³ All but one of the quasi-experimental studies had small sample sizes, limiting the generalizability of the data^{10-12,21-23} Most studies had short postoperative observation periods, with only four studies and one case report extending their observation to 28 days and beyond.^{8,14,17,19,23} Considering that Panhuizen et al.²³ detected rocuronium, and hypothetically sugammadex, after seven days but not after 28 days, future studies should consider an observation period of at least 28 days postoperatively.

Despite the limitations, there was consistency in the results and conclusions among studies. Articles examining efficacy consistently found sugammadex as an effective agent for reversing NMB in patients with severe renal failure.^{11,15,20,21,23} Similarly, studies on safety consistently reported no issues with recurarization or major AEs.^{11,14,15,17-21,23} Another strength of the literature was its overall quality. Despite being lower levels of evidence, most studies were

considered high or good quality, except for one poor quality article.¹⁰ While randomized-controlled trials are preferred, high-quality low level data can still contribute to building a consensus.

Summary

Sugammadex has been progressively establishing itself as the standard of practice for NMB antagonism. The current ASA guidelines on monitoring and antagonism of NMB make no reference to the use of sugammadex in patients with CRF, and the FDA does not currently advise its use in those with severe renal impairment. Nonetheless, instances of its application in patients with CRF have been noted in the clinical setting, along with corresponding case reports in the literature. As healthcare providers increasingly turn to the off-label use of sugammadex in individuals with CFR, they must stay informed about the latest research concerning its use in this population. A review of the literature suggests that sugammadex may be a safe and efficacious antagonist of rocuronium-induced NMB in adult patients with severe renal failure. However, more robust data with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are required to recommend its regular use in this population. Until more data is available, we suggest that providers administering sugammadex utilize neuromuscular monitoring and follow manufacturer dosing guidelines to mitigate patient risks.

References

1. Bridion [package insert]. Greenville, NC: Merck & Co., Inc; 2015. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2015/0222251bl.pdf
2. Hristovska AM, Duch P, Allingstrup M, Afshari A, Hristovska AM. Efficacy and safety of sugammadex versus neostigmine in reversing neuromuscular blockade in adults. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2017;2017(9):CD012763. <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012763>
3. Thilen SR, Weigel WA, Todd MM, et al. 2023 American Society of Anesthesiologists practice guidelines for monitoring and antagonism of neuromuscular blockade: a report by the American Society of Anesthesiologists task force on neuromuscular blockade. *Anesthesiology*. 2023;138(1):13-41. <https://doi.org/10.1097/aln.0000000000004379>
4. Doshu-Kajiura A, Suzuki J, Suzuki T. Prolonged onset and duration of action of rocuronium after accidental subcutaneous injection in a patient with chronic renal failure-a case report. *JA Clin Rep*. 2021;7(1):18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-021-00421-3>
5. Kurita S, Moriwaki K, Shiroyama K, Sanuki M, Toyota Y, Takebayashi M. Rocuronium-sugammadex use for electroconvulsive therapy in a hemodialysis patient: a case report. *JA Clinical Reports*. 2016;2(1):28-28. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-016-0055-4>
6. Lobaz S, Sammut M, Damodaran, A. Sugammadex rescue following prolonged rocuronium neuromuscular blockade with 'recurarisation' in a patient with severe renal failure. *BMJ Case Reports*. 2013;1-3. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bcr-2012-007603>
7. Navare SR, Garcia Medina O, Prielipp RC, Weinkauff JL. Sugammadex reversal of a large subcutaneous depot of rocuronium in a dialysis patient: a case report. *Anesthesia & Analgesia Practice*. 2019;12(10):375-377. <https://doi.org/10.1213/XAA.0000000000000934>
8. Ono Y, Fujita Y, Kajiura T, et al. Efficacy and safety of sugammadex in patients undergoing renal transplantation. *JA Clinical Reports*. 2018;4(1):56-56. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40981-018-0192-z>
9. Pfaff K, Tumin D, Tobias JD. Sugammadex for reversal of neuromuscular blockade in a patient with renal failure. *J Pediatr Pharmacol Ther*. 2019;24(3):238-241. <https://doi.org/10.5863/1551-6776-24.3.238>
10. Cammu G, Van Vlem B, van den Heuvel M, et al. Dialysability of sugammadex and its complex with rocuronium in intensive care patients with severe renal impairment. *British Journal of Anaesthesia: BJA*. 2012;109(3):382-390. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aes207>
11. Staals LM, Snoeck MM, Driessen JJ, Flockton EA, Heeringa M, Hunter JM. Multicentre, parallel-group, comparative trial evaluating the efficacy and safety of sugammadex in

- patients with end-stage renal failure or normal renal function. *Br J Anaesth*. 2008;101(4):492-497. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aen216>
12. Staals LM, Snoeck MM, Driessen JJ, et al. Reduced clearance of rocuronium and sugammadex in patients with severe to end-stage renal failure: a pharmacokinetic study. *Br J Anaesth*. 2010;104(1):31-39. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aep340>
 13. Dang D, Dearholt S, Bissett K, Ascenzi J, Whalen M. *Johns Hopkins Evidence-Based Practice for Nurses and Healthcare Professionals: Model and Guidelines*. 4th ed. Indianapolis, IN: Sigma Theta Tau International; 2022.
 14. Arslantas R, Cevik BE. Retrospective investigation of grafted kidney function after reversal of neuromuscular blockade using neostigmine or sugammadex. *Transplant Proc*. 2019;51(7):2265-2267. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2019.03.051>
 15. Carron M, Andreatta G, Pesenti E, et al. Impact on grafted kidney function of rocuronium-sugammadex vs cisatracurium-neostigmine strategy for neuromuscular block management. An Italian single-center, 2014-2017 retrospective cohort case-control study. *Perioperative Medicine*. 2022;11(1):3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13741-021-00231-2>
 16. Vargas M, Buonanno P, Sica A, et al. Effects of sugammadex plus rocuronium vs neostigmine plus cisatracurium during renal transplantation on graft function: a retrospective, case-control study. *Transplant Proc*. 2021;53(3):818-824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.transproceed.2020.09.012>
 17. Song S, Cho HB, Park SY, et al. Postoperative mortality in patients with end-stage renal disease according to the use of sugammadex: a single-center retrospective propensity score matched study. *Anesth Pain Med (Seoul)*. 2022;17(4):371-380. <https://doi.org/10.17085/apm.22189>
 18. Adams D, Tollinche L, Yeoh C, et al. Short-term safety and effectiveness of sugammadex for surgical patients with end-stage renal disease: a two-centre retrospective study. *Anaesthesia*. 2020;75(3):348-352. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anae.14914>
 19. Paredes S, Porter SB, Porter II IE, Renew JR. Sugammadex use in patients with end-stage renal disease: a historical cohort study. *Canadian Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2020;67(12):1789-1797. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12630-020-01812-3>
 20. Kim YS, Lim BG, Won YJ, Oh SK, Oh JS, Cho SA. Efficacy and safety of sugammadex for the reversal of rocuronium-induced neuromuscular blockade in patients with end-stage renal disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Medicina*. 2021;57(11). <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina57111259>

21. de Souza CM, Tardelli MA, Tedesco H, et al. Efficacy and safety of sugammadex in the reversal of deep neuromuscular blockade induced by rocuronium in patients with end-stage renal disease: A comparative prospective clinical trial. *European Journal of Anaesthesiology*. 2015;32(10):681-686. <https://doi.org/10.1097/EJA.0000000000000312>
22. Min KC, Lasseter KC, Marbury TC, et al. Pharmacokinetics of sugammadex in subjects with moderate and severe renal impairment. *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 2017;55(9):746-752. <https://doi.org/10.5414/CP203025>
23. Panhuizen IF, Gold SJA, Buerkle C, et al. Efficacy, safety and pharmacokinetics of sugammadex 4 mg kg⁻¹ for reversal of deep neuromuscular blockade in patients with severe renal impairment. *BJA: The British Journal of Anaesthesia*. 2015;114(5):777-784. <https://doi.org/10.1093/bja/aet586>
24. Vaidya SR, Aeddula NR. *Chronic Renal Failure*. StatPearls Publishing; 2022. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK535404/>
25. US Food & Drug Administration. Understanding unapproved use of approved drugs "off label." Published February 5, 2018. <https://www.fda.gov/patients/learn-about-expanded-access-and-other-treatment-options/understanding-unapproved-use-approved-drugs-label>. Accessed November 16, 2023.
26. Van Norman GA. Off-label use vs off-label marketing of drugs: part 1: off-label use-patient harms and prescriber responsibilities. *JACC Basic to Translational Science*. 2023;8(2):224-233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacbts.2022.12.011>
27. Wittich CM, Burkle CM, Lanier WL. Ten common questions (and their answers) about off-label drug use. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. 2012;87(10):982-990. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2012.04.017>
28. Joshi KG, Frierson RL. Off-label prescribing: how to limit your liability. *Current Psychiatry*. 2020;19(9):12. <https://doi.org/10.12788/cp.0035>